

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 2- Contractual and financial aspects of cross-service integration

D2.2 multi-actor energy performance contracting

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Executive summary

Energy efficiency interventions are key elements for achieving energy independence for citizen energy communities (CEC) and their definitive empowerment with respect to the current large monopolies. However, investments in energy efficiency are not currently attaining the rate needed, hindered by barriers such as lack of knowledge and awareness and personal resources, trust in new technology and expertise, high upfront costs, lack of access to finance and complex legal and contractual frameworks. Many of these challenges and barriers for establishing and managing highly efficient citizen energy communities can be overcome, at least significant part, with well-selected financial tools and instruments such as the Energy Performance Contracts.

The deliverable **D2.2 multi-actor energy performance contracting** provides guidelines for Citizen energy communities' actors to facilitate the energy efficiency services contracting phase, and to support the implementation of more energy efficiency measures, developed, and improved in real cases.

The report evaluates the Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), combined with Pay for Performance schemes (P4P), as commonly used tools to help the building owners to reach their energy and climate targets more quickly and effectively than the traditional implementation of the energy saving measure. It also identifies the most appropriate contracting models for each of NEON's CECs application case, for their deployment in case of multi-actor and multi-sector contractual arrangements. This work considers contracting between service providers and consumers, integration with performance schemes aimed at both service providers (e.g., between service providers and consumers), and integration with performance schemes aimed at both service providers (e.g., between utilities and aggregators) and consumers.

Based on the requirements identified within each of the NEON project CECs, within this task, adaptations and guidelines have been prepared and offered for improving the implementation of the EPC models combined to P4P mechanisms, and thus ensuring a successful implementation of additional energy efficiency services projects within the four NEON project's pilots.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
BMS	Building Management System
BOO	Build - Operate - Transfer
BOOT	Build – Own-Operate - Transfer
CEC	Citizen energy community
CHP	Combined Heat &Power
CPCU	California Public Utilities Commission
DSM	Demand side management
EE	Energy Efficiency
EES	Energy Efficiency Services
EN	European Norms
EPC	Energy Performance contracts
ESC	Energy Supply Contracting
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EU	European Union
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICF	Energy Optimisation programme
IEC	integrated energy contracting
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LSTM	long short-term memory network
M&V	Measurement and Verification
NVP	Net Present Value
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
LAC	Latin America and the Caribbean
P4P	Pay For Performance

1 Introduction

Citizen energy communities are a solution to achieve energy independence for citizens and their empowerment with respect to the current large monopolies. The integration of different types of services, as explained in deliverables D1.1 and D1.2 as well as in document D2.1 within the WP2 framework, adds an intrinsic value to the citizen energy communities as well as to each of the objectives and principles they represent.

However, high value-added services alone fail to exploit the full potential of CEC from an energy efficiency point of view due to several implicit factors including the lack of information and knowledge of the systems which integrate CECs, the parameters within the psychological spectrum such as trust and subjective perceptions, and finally, the lack of implementation mechanisms as well as the definition of the implementation scheme and the actors involved.

One of the current mechanisms that allows to reduce the CEC energy efficiency factors are the so-called innovative contractual schemes tailored to the specific needs of citizen energy communities and their integrated services. Thus, this deliverable will analyse and evaluate different contractual models and provide appropriate guidelines to facilitate the contracting phase of services within the range of application spectrum of energy communities.

Additionally, based on the synthesis of contractual schemes and the evaluation, the most appropriate contracting models for each application case will be identified, for further deployment in multi-actor and multi-sector contractual arrangements.

This document will consider contracting between service providers and consumers, as well as integration with performance schemes aimed at both service providers (e.g., between service providers and consumers), and integration with performance schemes aimed at both service providers and consumers, service providers (e.g., between utilities and aggregators) and consumers.

These contracting models will be specified with the objective of integrating energy efficiency services with other energy services (e.g., energy asset scheduling and DR) and with non-energy (e.g., ensuring grid security) and non-energy (e.g., ensuring comfort, health, and safety) benefits. Procurement models will be adapted to consider energy efficiency interventions and ensure better functioning of the community energy system although the main application will focus on the CEC buildings themselves. Another specific aspect that contracting schemes seeks to achieve is the reduction of capital expenditures (e.g., avoiding the cost of grid connections, reducing the size of transformers and inverters through better asset scheduling) and facility operating costs (e.g., flexibility gains and self-consumption could offset other costs). This will be done while sharing the benefits with CEC stakeholders.

2 Background

The provision of energy services is not a novel concept by any stretch of the imagination. Contracting one's energy use is an idea that goes back hundreds of years. Thus, *Compagnie Générale de Chauffage*, a French corporation, began providing energy contracting services with a primary emphasis on improving the efficiency of district heating systems more than a century ago. This marked the beginning of the "**Chauffage**" **modelling approach**. The supply side was the primary focus of the actions taken during this time.

In later years, Royal Dutch Shell brought the concepts behind this strategy to both the United Kingdom and the United States. The concept was designed to operate on the demand side, and the business would supply the client with conditioned space for 90% of what it now costs them. This led to the development of the **shared savings model**, which stipulated that the ESCO (Energy Service Company) and the customer would split the cost savings realised because of the energy efficiency measures implemented.

The term "**energy performance contracting**" was used to describe this idea somewhat later (EPC). The oil crisis that occurred in 1973 heightened people's awareness of how critical it was to reduce their overall use of energy. It was around this period that various energy services truly began to make a presence in the United States, and it is often believed that the "modern" kinds of energy services were formed from here.

Some energy services were made available to customers as part of the Demand Side Management programme (DSM), which required energy providers to participate in energy conservation activities on the client side (demand side). In most cases, these measures would consist of educational campaigns and subsidised financial aid for the purchase of energy-saving equipment. According to the study by Bergmash and Strid [2] at the beginning of the 1980s, there was an abrupt and unanticipated reduction in the cost of energy. As a result, both clients and many service providers showed less interest in purchasing energy-related services. When the payback time gets in a long-term range, the ESCOs that provided EPC with shared savings were unable to cover their investments. This was because the utilities that participated in the DSM programme would lose money on their services[1].

Additionally, the ESCOs that provided EPC with shared savings were unable to cover their investments. Several ESCOs filed for bankruptcy, and even the ESCOs that had guaranteed a certain amount of savings often lived up to their promises. This realisation led to the development of the EPC model, which was followed by the guaranteed savings model. According to this model, the customer would be responsible for the financing of the project rather than the ESCO, and in exchange, the ESCO would guarantee the savings. Since that time, the most common kind of EPC that has been used in the United States is the model known as guaranteed savings. On the opposite side, the practise of communal savings is still prevalent in Europe.

Over the course of the last fifteen years, there has been a rise in interest in energy efficiency. There are different reasons beyond this: the increased price of energy, the raised concerns about climate change, and about the security of energy supply because of rising political concerns and limited sources of oil and gas. There is a concerted effort being made by several countries, particularly in the European Union (EU), to increase energy efficiency via the promotion of energy services as a method of mitigating the effects of climate change and enhancing the safety of energy supply. There are many ways to contract for energy, and many of these ways have shown themselves to be viable business models on the market. When viewed from the perspective of the EU, the prospects for the future of energy services appear to be positive due to the growing awareness of the importance of energy efficiency, as well as the economic and environmental benefits that come with it, among policy makers, customers, and service providers alike.

3 Document’s structure

To achieve the overall objective of **T2.2 multi-actor energy performance contracting models and guidelines**, an approach has been proposed to perform the evaluation of the existing EPC, and to settle how the contraction models will be combined with P4P to guarantee an improved energy efficiency and an optimized building operation, following four main actions:

1. Analyze exiting EPCs (Energy Performance Contracting) and P4P schemas to determine what could be innovative for NEONs CECs,
2. Define how to combine P4P arrangements with the EPC,
3. Identify the gap between the existing EPCs and determine how they could be applied at the community level,
4. Create guidelines and steps that can be followed to facilitate the NEONs services contracting development within the CECs.

The work carried out within this task was a combination of:

- The individual work of the partners where the focus was on the identification of the contracting models, the related opportunities, and barriers.
- Collaborative sessions among T2.2 participants to review the identified models and schemas characterisations, to discuss the CEC requirements and to identify the gaps between the exiting and what could be applied at the community level.

Action	Involved partners
Review the EPC contracting existing models: involved parties, the contractor, the implementer, what is paid for, the funding, duration...	IDAE/R2M-AXPO
Review the P4P existing schemas.	IDAE/R2M -AXPO
Analysis and evaluation of the contracting models to define the opportunities and the added value, the risks, and barriers from the CEC point of view (SWOT analysis).	ALL
Analyze the CECs stakeholders' requirements (outputs of T1.1, T1.2) in terms of deployment layout of the energy systems, stakeholder system (legal framework, ownership, etc.), existing of any specific schema, financial structure.	ENGIE-GFM
Identify the gaps between the existing contracts and the CECs’ requirements.	R2M-IDAE
Analysis and evaluation of adaptability of the P4P combined with the EPCs within NEONs’ CECs.	R2M
Integration of guidelines for the contraction considering the social-cultural aspects, M&V and payment system adaptation to CECs and the financial contracting scenarios.	R2M-SIF
Deliverable preparation and submission.	ALL

Table 1 Task T2.2 action plan.

The activities committed according to the action listed previously has been reported in nine sections composing this deliverable:

- Section 01: An introduction to the deliverable giving an overview of the CECs potential added value as well as the objectives of the deliverable.
- Section 02: A background on the energy efficiency contracting concepts and the involved actors.
- Section 03: T2.2 work plan and the structure of the deliverable.
- Section 04: A definition of the energy efficiency service that has been applied for the whole of our investigation.
- Section 05: An overview of the main contracting structures that currently exist to address the factors implicit in energy efficiency.
- Section 06: The M&V procedures use in the performance-based contracting.
- Section 07: An analysis of advantages/disadvantages of performance contracting against traditional financial schemes and their main barriers and risks.
- Section 08: The gaps identification for the implementation of EPCs within the structure of citizen energy communities.
- Section 09: EPCs adaptation and the implementation guidelines to facilitate their implementation within NEONs' CECs.

4 Energy Service

The phrase "energy services" may be used to refer to a wide range of activities. In this section, we provide a definition that has obtained substantial consensus in recent years and that was/is applied in our investigation.

In a nutshell, a service is an "energy service" if it helps improve the efficiency with which energy is used and is in any way related to energy. There is a wide range of energy services available, ranging from simple billing that includes statistics on energy consumption to more complicated solutions. The process of negotiating a contract for more comprehensive energy services is sometimes referred to as "energy contracting," which is one of the terms that is commonly used to characterize the activity. The assumption of financial risk by the ESCO, in its capacity as the service provider, on the client's behalf is an essential component of any energy contract. It is possible that maximizing energy efficiency is not the main aim of the energy contract at all, but rather an unforeseen side effect. The former, like the Energy Performance Contract, has as its explicit goal the reduction of energy consumption at the demand end, whereas the latter, like the Energy Supply Contracting, has efficiency in mind only secondarily, as a means of optimizing the operation and economics of the service at the supply end. It is possible for usable energy to be provided to a building at a reduced cost as part of an energy service, rather than the actual fuel or electricity itself [3]. Some examples of this type of usable energy include heat, cooling, steam, compressed air, and other similar things. Finally, by implementing energy efficiency (EE) measures, it is possible to lower the cost of climate control in buildings. and to remain at a consistent temperature. Enhancing operating safety, air quality, comfort, and other aspects is also of the utmost importance.

According to the EU directive on energy end-use efficiency and energy services 2006/32/EC [6] passed by the European Union in 2006, energy services are defined as "the physical benefit, utility, or good derived from a combination of energy with energy efficient technology and/or with action, which may include the operations, maintenance, and control necessary to deliver the service, which is delivered on the basis of a contract and in normal circumstances has proven to lead to verifiable and measurable or verifiable and measurable or verify (EES). According to this theory, the terms "energy services" and "services for energy

efficiency" are interchangeable. The definition of an energy efficiency service in EN- 15900 and the idea of an energy service presented in the EU directive on energy end-use efficiency and energy services 2006/32/EC [6] (ESD) are relatively comparable to one another [4]. Both the ESD and EN- 15900 arrive to the same conclusion, which is that increasing energy production will lead to "increase in energy efficiency as a result of technological, behavioural, and/or economic changes." Additional EES examples may be found in the European Standard EN-15900 [8], such as the following:

- The intrinsic performance of buildings or equipment, which might refer to things like insulation, boiler efficiency, motor speed control, the efficiency of light bulbs, and other such things.
- The operation and maintenance of installations: efficiency in operation (more automatic buildings, logistic and layout optimization), enhanced maintenance, ongoing optimization of overall tech items.
- Energy management system implementation: the monitoring of the energy system
- Users' actions: education and advocacy for energy-saving practices

Energy services, from the most basic to the most complex, are shown in a value chain in the accompanying picture. In practice, the position of energy services in the value chain might vary from project to project due to the varying scope of energy services.

Figure 1: Energy service portfolio.

Some of the models of energy contracts to be evaluated in the NEON context may be found by looking at the more sophisticated energy services. The most cutting-edge energy contracts provide a suite of efficiency upgrades all in one convenient package. "A complete energy service concept to execute energy efficiency projects in buildings or industrial facilities according to reduced project cycle cost," [3] is how Grazer Energieagentur defines energy contracting.

Several distinct varieties of contracts are now in circulation. EPC, ESC (Energy Supply Contracting), IEC (integrated energy contracting), and Chauffage are all evaluated in this report.

Next, a diagram of the energy supply network is presented. On the left is main energy (coal, oil, and so on), while on the right are contracts for secondary energy and energy conservation. While the figure's boundaries aren't as distinct, they do show potential places where energy contracts may be in effect.

Figure 2: the energy value chain.

5 Energy performance contracting overview

As stated in the previous sections, the objective of this document is to provide the necessary tools for the analysis and synthesis of the characteristics of the different alternative contracting schemes and/or their combination within the framework of citizen energy communities.

Thus, in this general section, an overview of the main contracting structures that currently exist to address the factors implicit in energy efficiency is presented. Likewise, their differential characteristics are presented with the main objective of laying the foundations for their subsequent application to the energy community schemes present in the NEON project.

As stated before, the European Directive 2012/27 on energy efficiency states that an energy performance contracting implies a contractual arrangement between the beneficiary and the provider of an energy efficiency improvement measure (usually ESCOs), verified and monitored during the whole term of the contract, where investments (work, supply or service) in that measure are paid for in relation to a contractually agreed level of energy efficiency improvement or other agreed energy performance criterion, such as financial saving.

In this way, a formal definition of such contracting schemes is established in which there is a direct link between a supplier and a beneficiary, with energy efficiency indicators as the basis of the business model. In this case, the figure of the supplier may be composed of several actors as will be seen in the following sections. Likewise, the figure of the beneficiary in the case of citizen energy communities can also be a novelty both in terms of the legal figure and in terms of fiscal and even psychological aspects.

The EPC paradigm of energy contracting is extensively used. This kind of contract is ideal for endeavors of a substantial size. The EPC is a one-stop shop for all the energy efficiency needs, and the ESCO provides

the beneficiaries with all the tools they need to start saving money right now. Energy savings from EPC projects average between 20 and 30 percent (and may go as high as 50 percent).

An EPC contract is distinguished by the fact that it is performance oriented; outcomes are evaluated in relation to an agreed-upon standard (energy usage before the project implementation). This allows for a direct comparison between energy use throughout the project period and after its completion. The ESCO's compensation is tied directly to the success of the project.

The EPC project is paid for out of the money saved on energy use. So, in essence, initiatives are self-sustaining. Initial capital might be provided by the ESCO, the client, or an outside entity. Energy management systems, servicing and optimization of technical facilities, behavioral adjustments, and so on are commonplace examples of the kind of things that may be done to reduce a building's carbon footprint.

5.1 EPC Existing models

First, as it is one of the most iconic schemes in the European territorial scope, the different casuistries of EPC contracting will be analyzed. The main ones are three and below are their technical foundations and their main characteristics.

5.1.1 Shared saving model

In the Shared Saving model [5], ESCOs sign a financing and performance contract with energy customers (in the present case, CECs), being responsible for designing, financing, and implementing an EPC project. ESCOs are requested to verify the energy savings during the contract period and fixed portions of the energy savings are paid to ESCOs over a fixed period, leaving almost “zero risk” to clients. Thus, the performance is related to energy cost savings and ESCOs take both performance and credit risks.

Figure 3 Shared Saving Model.

Thus, in the EPC of shared savings, the contractor fully finances the implementation of the project and obtains a percentage of the savings for a determined period, once the facility is upgraded. Internationally, many governments are implementing efforts to promote the EPC model of shared savings, which was the most widely used, for example, in North American energy efficiency businesses in the past decades. ESCOs

in that region were integrating financing with EPC financing within the service package, which was very attractive to their customers.

Fast-out EPCs are a variation of shared savings ESPCs. In this modality, the contract does not have a fixed term. The latter is not defined, and payments are not made until the cost of the project - a predetermined amount - has been paid in full to the ESCO. This type of contract became the most widely used after some clients decided to suspend payments to the ESCO claiming that they were receiving "unfairly high amounts of money". This modality usually has a maximum period of duration, after which payments must cease.

On the one hand, this design reduces the ESCO's level of risk, as payments can be made over a longer period in case the expected savings have not yet been achieved. On the other hand, if the level of savings is higher than expected, the ESCO does not have the right to earn more money based on these savings.

In the following figure we can obtain the basic implementation scheme of the contracting structure based on the shared savings:

Figure 4: Project implementation basic scheme for shared savings EPC.

On the following picture you can observe the outline of the payment period:

Figure 5: Outline of the payment period for shared savings EPC.

5.1.2 Guaranteed saving model

Another most often deployed EPC strategy is the guaranteed saving concept. As part of the Guaranteed Savings approach, ESCOs will plan and carry out the EPC project, but they will not provide any funding themselves. The ESCOs guarantee that the energy savings will be adequate to repay debt service obligations. In this instance, the performance is tied to energy saving level and ESCOs carry the performance risk, while the consumers take the credit risk.

Figure 6: Guaranteed saving model (EPC).

In a guaranteed savings project, the contractor will sign a turnkey contract with its client, financing will be obtained through a third party, and the contractor will guarantee in an addendum to the original agreement that it is committed to reimburse any stated savings not achieved. This contractual arrangement has become the most widely used type of EPC worldwide. In fact, its advantages for the client are many:

- It has greater access to loans and leasing schemes, since it is the owner of the facilities and assets
- It obtains better terms on loans and pays no additional interest rate added by the ESCO

The contractual documents for this type of contract are traditional and easy to understand because the turnkey arrangement is a traditional engineering, procurement, and construction (EPC) contract and can be either a loan or a financial leasing scheme.

Project implementation scheme:

Figure 7: Implementation scheme for the guaranteed saving model and its outline of the payment period.

5.1.3 Chauffage model

In Chauffage model, ESCOs are responsible for the operation and maintenance of complete energy infrastructure for energy consumers, and they shoulder the energy expenses. ESCOs manage and alter the energy system for energy consumers by self-financing according to goals in the contract. ESCOs earn full energy savings if they reach the objectives. Otherwise, they need to pay for the shortfall to energy users as compensation. The performance is tied to energy cost reductions and ESCOs accept both performance and credit risks as in shared saving mod

Figure 8: Chauffage model.

In a chauffage contract, the ESCO owns the energy conversion systems placed on the customer's premises. Thus, the chiller plant may be used to convert power to cooling systems, and a boiler room can be utilized to convert fuel to steam. Under this structure, when the contract is signed, the ESCO will run, maintain, and pay the customer's energy bills, pay the energy bills for the conversion system, as well as invest in boosting the efficiency of the system. The ESCO offers "converted" energy to its client at a specific reduced cost and fulfilling a defined quality level of energy delivery throughout the contract time.

The discount contract is not tied to a particular project; moreover, the ESCO does not need to submit an adequate design before signing the contract. What happens is that, after signing the contract, the ESCO makes whatever improvements the system requires: the more the ESCO's maintenance and operating costs are reduced, the more the profitability of the system increases. Chauffage schemes represent the best incentives for ESCOs to be efficient in providing services.

Many customers seek this type of contract, not necessarily because of the energy savings it can produce, but because they wish to delegate the management of their converter system to concentrate their resources and capabilities on their line of resources and capabilities on their line of business.

Project implementation scheme:

Figure 9: Implementation scheme of the Chauffage model (EPC).

5.2 Methodology of developing an EPC

In some cases, an EPC contract that includes simple explanations that blur its purpose (i.e., project development and implementation) may appear to be unclear, mysterious, and difficult to understand by ESCO's potential clients. For example, saying that in an EPC contract where "the ESCO covers the costs of the project and then the client reimburses them based on savings", while not incorrect, may be insufficient to explain the complexity of the contract (Ambience, 2020).

An EPC contract is indeed a transaction whereby an ESCO contractor sells an investment project to a client, even if the investment outcome is not known precisely when the first commitment is made. In other words, an ESCO contractor sells the idea that there is some potential for energy savings, and that the ESCO can identify and quantify these savings, as well as to design and implement a turnkey project to obtain them. Making this sale is not an easy task, especially in markets such as LAC where customers are not yet very familiar with how EPC contracts work. However, it is possible to facilitate this process by following the methodology illustrated (Pre-contracting phase):

5.2.1 Pre-contracting phase

The first phase involves the collection and analysis of energy data and the benchmarking of all significant consumptions through a simple energy audit. Then a technical feasibility study is performed to check every condition for the realization and the installation of the new energy saving measures and an economic and social analysis is performed to develop a preliminary cost estimation and to estimate the expected benefits. The pre-contracting phase diagram is described below:

Figure 10: Pre-contracting phase.

5.2.2 Contracting phase

The contracting phase is the pivotal phase of EPC projects because the main calculations and quantifications on the terms of the contract (duration, energy savings guarantee, consumption baseline, Measurement and Verification methodology) are determined in this phase. The accuracy and adequacy of terms defined here will contribute to lower risks for the ESCO as well as better performance gain for the client. After the design of the contract and the definition of the engineering projects required for the implementation of the EPC, the selected energy measures are carried out.

Figure 11: Contracting phase.

5.2.3 Performance phase

The performance phase is the last phase and starts after the installation of the new equipment. It is divided into two actions:

- Operation and monitoring: monitoring of energy consumptions and implementation of active control.
- Measurement and verification: a regular measurement procedure is done to determine both energy and cost savings; the most common used protocol is the IPMVP (International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol), that calculate savings by comparing the measured consumption before and after the implementation of the EPC project, adjusting for changes in conditions.

Figure 12: Performance phase.

5.3 Benefits and risks

EPC programs are relatively recent initiatives that aim to encourage the implementation of energy efficiency measures. These programs make it feasible to reduce energy consumption as well as CO₂ emissions. In addition, does not need any initial capital investment, which means that anybody may participate in its success [7].

Since in an EPC the savings are required to be calculated over the course of the entire term of the contract, this encourages the improvement of energy monitoring, but at the same time it involves some risks of various types. These risks include an economic risk associated with the variation in the cost of energy, a financial risk (when a third-party financing is required), an operational risk associated with an unexpected variation in baseline conditions, and a measurement risk that manifests itself as poor data quality or inaccurate metering. Commissioning costs for an EPC project might fluctuate greatly depending on the degree of difficulty of the work being performed. In less than three years, many investments in commissioning will pay for themselves via cost savings. Commissioning may reduce future equipment maintenance expenditures, downtime, and replacement prices by 15 percent or more. When faults with the performance of equipment are discovered while the equipment is still covered by its manufacturer's warranty, the agency can reduce its costs by encouraging the equipment manufacturers and ESCOs to fix the flaws. In addition, the EPC incorporates incentive programs like as P4P, which may encourage customers to be more responsible about the monitoring of their consumptions. Increased building staff knowledge and improved equipment operation are two of the many benefits that come from commissioning an EPC. Project commissioning provides the agency employees with the skills necessary to optimize the operating conditions and control of the equipment. Optimization at the system level improves the coordination between the many building systems and boosts the overall performance of the structure. Longer equipment life, greater operational reliability, and increased operational efficiency are all benefits of improved system control.

During the building phase of the project, commissioning facilitates better planning, coordination, and communication between the ESCO and the agency. This makes it simpler to start up the equipment. This results in shorter punch lists and fewer call-backs being needed to fix problems. Commissioning also encourages a speedier and more seamless start-up of the equipment because of the rigorous testing operations that are performed on both the equipment and the control systems.

Commissioning allows front-end performance responsibility and quality control since the avoidance of issues is less expensive than the resolution of problems. It is possible that this will provide fast feedback to specialists on the dynamic performance of their design. If the equipment fails, and proper commissioning has been performed, liability worries may be reduced.

Greater building control, which results in increased thermal comfort and improved interior air quality, is perhaps the greatest advantageous effect that can be gained from commissioning a structure. These help to reduce the number of complaints about the temperature from tenants and employee absenteeism, which in turn boosts staff retention and saves the organization money. Although they are difficult to measure, the annual health and productivity benefits of a pleasant facility are likely to be worth more than the year energy and operating cost savings. This is the case even though the benefits are difficult to assess.

The purchase of a wide variety of building supplies and services may be accomplished with the help of energy performance contracts. The ESCO could also provide a wide variety of repair and maintenance services in addition to the actual installation of the equipment, as part of the EPC project. These services may include re-installation of damaged or missing controls, as well as repairs to leaks in chilled water or landscape irrigation pipelines. In certain cases, the ESCO is the party that is responsible for doing preventive maintenance as well as repairs on all newly installed equipment. It is very uncommon for pre-existing maintenance contracts to undergo periodic renegotiation to alter the range of services provided, and in certain instances, these contracts may even be terminated altogether due to the introduction of cutting-edge technology. Additionally, the ESCO may propose to take on responsibility for the operation and even the maintenance of any existing machinery. For instance, the ESCO may propose to provide remote monitoring and modification of temperature setpoints by means of a computerized building control system. This may be one of the services that they provide.

Because the facility retains ownership of any equipment that is installed, the ESCO is responsible for providing documentation for every equipment that is installed. This documentation includes as-built drawings and operating instructions. Additionally, the ESCO educates the staff working at the plant on how to operate and maintain the various pieces of equipment. ESCOs could even foot the tab for plant staff to take part in manufacturer-sponsored training sessions if it's in their best interest. It is possible to arrange the cost structure of an EPC in such a way that it will permit the retention of an ESCO-provided maintenance manager or technicians to support the long-term performance of a project in those organizations that have a limited amount of in-house maintenance expertise. As a consequence of the efforts put into an EPC project, the lifespan of the equipment is often extended, which results in a reduction in the expenses associated with its replacement. The number of essential preventive maintenance jobs will need to be completed less often if the runtime hours are cut down. Better monitoring of the conditions in which the machine is being used may make it possible to increase the reliability of the machine's performance.

Better building maintenance may result in increased satisfaction among building occupants with their working conditions and a reduction in the number of sick days taken.

Long-term analysis is required to evaluate the overall benefits that come from having the ability to quantify the worth of the money saved on operations and maintenance (e.g., reduced equipment repair and replacement occurs over a period of 20 years). If the ESCO initiative is successful in drastically reducing the amount of time existing agency maintenance personnel spends on hot and cold comfort calls, then that staff will have more time to devote to preventive tactics.

EPC projects have the potential to result in the capture of large O&M (Operation and Maintenance) savings provided proper planning and perseverance are used. Think of performance-based maintenance as an all-encompassing and ongoing form of commissioning; each year of the 20-year performance contract, the HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) system must have its filters cleaned, its controls optimized, its drive belts fixed, and its conditioning system serviced. Condition-based maintenance should also be based on observable data such as operating time, vibration analysis, thermographic and ultrasonic testing, and efficiency. For a maintenance plan to be effective, its foundation must consist of correct information on the state of the apparatus being maintained.

5.4 Application examples

5.4.1 Project description

The Dublin City Council decided to use an Energy Performance Contract model to carry out upgrades to the Ballymun, Finglas, and Markievicz Sports and Fitness Centres, rather than carrying out these works using more traditional methods. This decision was made since leisure centers are typically high consumers of energy.

5.4.2 Energy Measures

The three sports and exercise facilities all received their finished energy improvements, which comprised the following:

1. Improvements to the Building Management System (also known as BMS)
2. Rebuilding of the CHP (Combined Heat and Power) and installation of power modulation controllers (Finglas)
3. A brand new 110 kWh combined heat and power plant and power modulation controllers (Ballymun)
4. Installation of lighting controls and an upgrade to LED lighting.
5. An innovative approach to the cooling of air handling units.
6. The placement of the plant with a high modulation boiler.
7. The installation of new controllers for the pool pumpers

5.4.3 Results

Measurement and verification, often known as M&V, have been performed on the buildings on a regular basis. According to the most recent numbers provided by M&V, the EPC project was able to save Dublin City Council around €122,000 on its expenses and costs in its first year of operation, in addition to achieving an average energy savings of 38%. During the whole time that this contract is in effect, the ESCO will

continue to provide management assistance to DCC for the M&V process. Due to the overwhelming success of the project, DCC has begun work on a second EPC that will include several buildings; the development of this second project has reached an advanced level.

5.5 Pay for performance schemas overview

P4P schemes' organizational framework is comparable to that of Energy Performance Contracting (EPC). The European Union (EU) has EPC, most prominently in the public sector (such as hospitals, universities, etc.) and to a lesser degree in the private (industrial and commercial) sectors. However, it has relatively restricted use in residential and minor commercial structures. High transaction costs have limited testing to the residential sector, and only for very big construction blocks [9][10]. As an alternative, P4P programs use metering tools to quantify energy savings. Using an aggregator approach, they are being tested in real-world small and medium businesses and homes and extensive property portfolios [11].

P4P models have yet to be implemented in the EU, despite the potential advantages they would provide. The European Commission hopes to create a business model that will integrate P4P schemes and EPC in this regard. The purpose of this is to increase EPC adoption and offer performance-based programs to the EU market. The completion of these steps will make energy efficiency initiatives marketable investments.

This has the potential to leverage private finance, which would increase the pace of building renovations in the EU. The overarching objective is to create and evaluate novel transaction models that allow building energy efficiency improvements to provide value via:

- Financial incentives that encourage building owners to use energy-saving solutions that also benefit the electrical grid.
- Positively impacting peak capacity needs and ramping reserves are capacity methods that compensate energy efficiency to decrease power consumption indefinitely.
- Risk of paying for potential energy savings that never materialize is eliminated program funding.

Figure 13: Relationship between EPC & P4P.

There is a wide variety of programs that are included in the pay-for-performance category; however, at their most fundamental level, these programs are designed to monitor and provide incentives for good performances (such as decreased energy consumption, emission levels, or demand response actions) as they take place. So, these mechanisms reward end-users or aggregators for providing better performances, based on metered and verified data, against a business-as-usual (i.e., baseline) scenario and focus not only on the implementation of new equipment or systems but also on their performance.

Pay-for-performance (P4P) schemes aim to deliver greater and more persistent energy savings by compensating (paying) energy efficiency resources based on a comparison of metered energy consumption and modelled counterfactual energy consumption. The amount of money saved on energy bills is the metric that is used to evaluate how well the energy efficiency project is working, and payments are provided on an ongoing basis "when the savings materialize." The accomplishment of this task guarantees that the project will be successful.

Figure 14: Basic performance scheme of P4P.

The entity that is often willing to pay to stimulate energy savings is either a government agency or a utility company, and the funds are then directed to the projects that will benefit from those savings. These projects might be structured in the way of energy performance contracting, which can be done even if it is not required to do so.

To this day, the bulk of pay-for-performance programs focused on buildings have been controlled by utilities that are mandated to fulfil energy efficiency resource criteria. These utilities shall ensure that buildings achieve these standards. In the European Union, these regulations are most usually referred to as energy efficiency requirement schemes, however further uses might be imagined. For example, models that are based on pay-for-performance may potentially be used in the same way to capacity mechanisms. System operators often create these schemes to ensure that enough capacity will be able to supply demand, particularly during peak hours. This is especially important in situations when demand is expected to be at its highest level. This is done to accommodate load requirements.

Even if they are not the first or best solution to issues with the adequateness and reliability of the power supply, in regions where they are implemented, energy efficiency is often excluded from participation, either explicitly or implicitly. There are a few conditions that must be met before energy efficiency may be allowed to take part in an auction. A P4P strategy would require the administrative body to enter contracts with aggregators or building owners to acquire the energy efficiency that was determined by the data collected from the meters that were used to measure energy consumption. Using the data from smart

meters, it is possible to track results by time and location, as well as to value the contribution of energy efficiency to reducing capacity requirements.

5.6 Existing schemas

The majority of P4P schemes need extra compensation, at least for a couple of years, to guarantee that the anticipated savings are realized and continue to accrue. Historically, pay-for-performance programs have often compensated energy efficiency cost reductions in one of two basic methods [12]:

- Standard offer programs
- Bidding programs

5.6.1 Standard offer programs

In standard offer programs, the utility determines the price that it is willing to pay for a measurable unit of savings as part of a standard offer program. To ensure that the savings are realized, the utility company engages into long-term contracts with implementers (such as ESCOs, contractors, major customers, or other implementers). These contracts typically range from 5 to 15 years in length. The discretionary involvement of utilities as program managers is limited by standard offer programs since these systems do neither score bids nor negotiate contracts. When the target amount of money is saved, or when there is no more money left in the financing pool, an offer is acceptable.

5.6.2 Bidding programs

Program implementers, aggregators, and clients are all able to compete for contracts via the use of bidding programs. These contracts outline a certain level of cost reduction that must be attained over several years. The program may be organized as an auction or as another kind of competitive solicitation, in which price and a few other elements are taken into consideration to choose the winning bidders.

5.7 Basic design features

P4P programs are less specific than EPC model and may include a diverse spectrum of cases but are characterized by the same developing phases without being strictly related to energy savings, the pre-contracting phase, the contracting phase, and the performance phase. Furthermore, P4P programs consist of some common design features, namely [13]:

- The type of approach followed: P4P can be applied in different contexts, such as the energy efficiency programmes or sharing flexibility and capacity mechanisms.
- The administration in charge: different entities can be responsible for the administration of the P4P programs, such as utilities, implementers/aggregators, like ESCOs, or public authorities.
- The roles of different actors: the administrator, whose role generally comprises budgeting, financial and contract management, the implementer, who develops the project and implements the measures, and in some cases a dedicated measurement provider, responsible for collecting and analysing data.
- The source of funding: P4P programs can be funded by utilities, whose funds comes from ratepayers, or by third parties financing.
- The customer segment: some programs are especially focused on commercial or industrial customers with a high potential for savings, but typically are open to all customers segments.
- Eligible measures under the programme: depending on each programme's goal and purpose, there may be a combination of multiple measures, such as device replacement, operational and behavioural improvement, or installation of new equipment.

5.8 Design

In the following paragraphs, we will discuss the payment flows and performance assessment of P4P systems.

5.8.1 The Continuum of Financial Transactions

P4P programs provide financial help for energy efficiency measures on an ongoing basis, that is, when savings are generated from the implementation of the measures. The following aspects were considered throughout the planning stages of the program:

5.8.2 Who is going to pay for this?

It is a duty of a governmental authority, a utility, or any other organisation for that matter, to distribute the monies to the entity implements energy efficiency measures. Ratepayers or taxpayers often foot the bill for the program's overhead costs, although funds may be distributed in a wide variety of ways.

5.8.3 Who will be the one to benefit?

The ultimate beneficiaries of the program are end users such as families and businesses; however, it is not assured that these end users would earn compensation that is proportional with the amount of energy that they save. In fact, aggregators or program implementers, the number of which varies depending on the program, frequently carry out the function of acting as middlemen between end users and the organisation that is responsible for distributing payments. End users get services from these aggregators, which motivates them to lower the amount of energy they consume. Additionally, these aggregators have the option to decide whether they will share performance advantages with end users. Contractual agreements are often negotiated between the entity that provides payments and the aggregator, as well as between aggregators and end-consumers. In other situations, these negotiations also take place between aggregators and end- customers. Aggregators have the option of forming partnerships with subcontractors, if they are permitted to do so.

5.8.4 How much?

The amount of money that can be saved is directly proportional to the quantity of energy that can be preserved. A price per unit is often established in advance for most transactions. It is also conceivable that it is the result of a bidding system, in which several aggregators compete against one another on a range of qualities, one of which is the price at which they propose to give the service. Another possibility is that it is the output of a random process. The amount of gasoline that is conserved might influence the prices. The option to assess a higher fee for more labour-intensive strategies to cut energy use is one that is within the scope of governmental authorities to make (e.g., deeper savings, hard-to-reach sectors, longer lifetimes, complex measures, etc.). There is a potential that to get the cash, extra conditions will need to be satisfied (e.g., minimum project size, etc.). There is no logical reason why remuneration couldn't be contingent entirely on how well an employee did their job. In the case that some of the payment is not going to be based on the amount of energy that may be saved by metering, other benchmarks have been set. It's possible that there may be a cap imposed on the total amount that will be paid out as well.

5.8.5 Where does this lead?

The eligibility of projects may be reliant on a wide range of factors, including the scale of the energy savings, the quantity of fuel saved, customers, industries, geographical location, metrics, and the purpose that is being attempted to be accomplished (energy savings or demand response). Either the rules may

declare that activities are ineligible to get benefits from the program, or they may focus the program's attention expressly toward specific segments or activities. Either way, the rules are likely to be implemented in one of two ways. The degree to which a Pay-for-Performance program need to be "measure-agnostic" is something that must be taken into consideration. Usually, the program will provide recommendations on how to generate the baseline upon which the energy savings are computed. These recommendations may take the form of guidelines, regulations, or an in-depth methodology.

5.8.6 When?

P4P systems are comprised of a variety of fundamental aspects, such as the duration of the program, the frequency of payments, and the criteria for how payments are first launched. If the project is not finished in a satisfactory manner, it is possible to combine up-front payment with penalties for poor performance. Using a project is one way to accomplish this goal. Participants in the project or aggregators might potentially profit from this in terms of controlling some of the early expenditures connected with their own projects. If the amount of verified savings is less than the amount of contracted savings, it is possible, for instance, to levy fines against implementers for under-delivery of energy savings such as requiring implementers to install additional measures.

5.8.7 An assessment of previous accomplishments

P4P projects link remuneration to cost reductions via the use of data gathered from energy meters. The design of the program considers and incorporates the following factors and considerations:

5.8.7.1 How exactly are all these figures compiled?

P4P programs need a reliable collection of meter readings; nevertheless, the use of smart meters is not strictly required for these kinds of programs. On the other hand, P4P systems often use cutting-edge technology for the purpose of energy metering. The type of technology that is required to participate in the program can vary, ranging from advanced meter reading, which transmits information from the consumption site to the utility, to advanced metering infrastructure (AMI, also known as "smart meters"), which establishes two-way communication between the consumption site and the utility. Both of these types of technology are necessary for participation in the program. Participation in the program requires possession of both forms of technological apparatus. The frequency of data surveying is something that is decided upon during the design phase of the program and is subject to alter dependent on the needs of the program as well as the technical capabilities that are now available. Aggregators can provide their customers with the appropriate metering equipment as part of the range of services that they offer.

5.8.7.2 How exactly does one go about analysing the data?

Data analysis is essential to provide a baseline for comparison. The bulk of these applications need access to some historical data, and to "correct" this data set for factors such as the weather, they use data analytics. The analysis of data may also be helpful in the management of portfolios consisting of multiple different smaller initiatives. It is feasible that this will make it simpler to calculate the overall amount of energy that will be used by a "fleet" of buildings. Data analytics can also be used to help account for measures that are typically difficult to track, such as behaviour and operational upgrades, or to account for a mix of investment upgrades and behavioural measures. Both applications are examples of situations in which data analytics can be useful. The application of data analytics in any of these two scenarios is an example of a circumstance in which it may be useful (thus better considering how end users are running and maintaining the equipment).

5.9 Benefits and risks

The goals that are intended to be accomplished by a particular program will determine both its potential advantages and potential drawbacks. P4P can help in assessing savings and motivating persistence in savings from complex, multi-measure efficiency projects including those with behavioural or operational changes, where it is difficult to deem savings in advance. In general, P4P can aid in assessing savings and motivating persistence in savings. In addition, P4P schemes make monitoring systems and devices better, and they may contribute to the creation of standardized measurement techniques that can be used to determine a baseline and evaluate performances[12].

On the other side, pay-for-performance programs add the performance risk, which may be broken down into two subcategories: implementation risk and assessment risk. This risk refers to the chance that a certain portfolio of P4P projects will achieve the expected savings [14]:

5.10 Application examples

5.10.1 Actors involved

The following actors are involved in the scheme:

- The California Senate sets energy efficiency goals (Senate Bill 350).
- The California Assembly has passed Assembly Bill 793, which mandates that customers have access to real-time data on their energy use and requests that weather-normalized, meter-based cost reductions be given priority (Assembly Bill 802).
- The California Public Utilities Commission (CPUC, the regulator) mandates that utility companies purchase energy saving programs that have been planned and carried out by a third party (Decision 16-08-019). PG&E, an energy utility, procures third-party programs, rewards contractors and evaluates (sometimes with the CPUC) samples of up to 10% of participating customers or completed projects each quarter.
- Third party aggregators — three contractors with four program contracts — deliver energy savings (Franklin Energy, who has two programme contracts; ICF; and Richard Heath and Associates) using data-driven feedback to inform future program interventions.
- Customers benefit from energy efficiency measures and co-finance investments where applicable.
- Electricity and natural gas consumers pay a surcharge on their bills to fund the energy efficiency program portfolio. Consumers benefit from system savings stemming from energy efficiency programs, with P4P programs ensuring that ratepayers are getting value for money, given that their investment is tied to performance.

5.10.2 Measures

Each program has different offers for customers, with contractors having the flexibility to choose from a wide variety of measures and approaches including retrofits, operational measures, and behavioural measures, including variable pricing. The programs are:

- The Home Energy Optimisation programme (ICF) offers smart thermostats, tuning and optimisation of equipment, such as air conditioners and water heaters, lighting, and monthly energy efficiency progress reports.
- Home Energy Rewards (Franklin Energy) offers home energy use analysis with recommendations, energy savings kits and discounted energy efficient products, as well as the possibility of full-home energy retrofits (HVAC equipment and fabric improvements).

- The WatterSaver Package and Residential Energy Fitness Program (Richard Heath and Associates) offers rebates on high efficiency, hybrid electric and heat pump water heaters, as well as free in-home assessments and upgrades to smart thermostats and enhanced time delay relay. Some no-cost water consumption reduction measures are also offered.
- Comfortable Home Rebates (Franklin Energy) offers home maintenance and fabric improvements, as well as upgrades to more efficient lighting, HVAC, water heating and pool pumps.

5.10.3 Performance assessment

The CalTRACK method is used to calculate a counterfactual against which observed energy consumption is compared (like IVMVP Method 3). The method accounts for weather variation and time of the week. Hourly electric meter reads are needed, which are available daily through Green Button Connect with a 24-hour delay. Customers can agree to share their data with any of the contracted third parties through the Share My Data platform.

5.10.4 Reward mechanism

Household participants are not rewarded on a P4P basis. The third-party aggregators are rewarded based on the performance of their portfolio of households. Compensation is provided to third-party aggregators monthly over the two-year period based on the expected lifetimes of the measures. Payment was initially scheduled to be annual, but the frequency of payments was increased to align with contractor investment outgoings and the associated risks more closely being taken. Compensation rates per kWh and terms agreed upon are commercially sensitive.

5.10.5 Achievements

It's too early to say now, with only two programs fully launched and only one of the programs mature. Programs are also quite small (less than \$10 million dollars spent to date, compared to an annual spend of \$270-280 million on the program portfolio).

5.10.6 Issues of interest for setting P4P schemes

What have the main drivers been?

- Policy and regulatory drivers for ambitious energy efficiency programs, third-party contracting, and the use of real-time data.
- Policy and regulation driven by climate goals, the increasing variation in the value of energy savings by time of day and year, and the need to improve the cost-effectiveness of programs funded by ratepayers.

6 Performance Measurement and Verification

Uncertainty about the achievement of the anticipated savings and the possibility of legal conflict over the scope of performance guarantees are two of the primary factors that stand in the way of profitability in performance-based contracting. Since compensation is bound up with performance, in this type of contracts it is important to plan a clear and reliable M&V procedure to avoid or limit these barriers.

To accurately determine the profit, it is necessary to define in the contract:

- The measurement method.
- The baseline of consumption.
- The savings calculation.

6.1 The measurement method

The process of using the measurements to accurately assess the benefits obtained because of the implementation of a performance-based contracting program is the procedure that is referred to as a measuring technique [16].

The protocol is based on the principle that savings cannot be measured but can be determined by making comparisons between the situation before and after the implementation of the project and making appropriate adjustments to depending on changes in conditions. According to this principle, savings cannot be measured but can be determined by making comparisons between the situation before and after the implementation of the project.

- Installation, configuration, calibration, and maintenance of measuring instruments.
- Data collection and visualization.
- Development of a computation method and acceptable estimates. Measurement activities consist of some or all the following points: installation, configuration, calibration, and maintenance of measuring instruments.
- Reporting, as well as quality assurance and evaluation of the reports by a third party.

Measurement activities are integrated with those relating to efficiency projects, as shown in the figure 15 (measurement activities are written in bold):

Figure 15: Timeline of efficiency processes.

Measurement techniques can be used for the following purposes:

- Increase energy savings.
- Document the necessary financial transactions (in the case of performance-based contracts).
- Increase the possibility of financing for efficiency projects.
- Improve the management of plant operations and maintenance.
- Improve the management of the energy budget.
- Allow you to calculate emissions reductions.
- Make it possible to disseminate the savings obtained and raise awareness among the public.

The fundamental principles of a measurement program are:

- Accuracy: measurement reports should always be as accurate as possible in relation to the budget made available.
- Completeness: a project report should consider all effects of the project; significant effects must be quantified, and others estimated.
- Conservativeness: where judgments are made on uncertain grounds, measurement procedures should underestimate savings.

- Consistency

There are a variety of time periods over which the same project may be carried out.

- Relevance: savings should be determined by measuring the most important performance parameters, while others can be estimated.
- Transparency: all measurement activities should be explained precisely.

6.2 The baseline scenario

The baseline scenario, which depicts what would have transpired in the absence of the deployment of the efficiency retrofits, is the most important aspect to consider when calculating the amount of money that may be saved [17].

To provide a comprehensive description of the baseline situation, you need both specific technical knowledge and educated assumptions. This is dependent on the approach that was used to measure it. Even though M&V is a field that is still developing, best practices have been established, and these practices have been documented in several guidelines. One of the most popular protocols is called the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP), and it offers a variety of options and methods for determining a baseline and estimating savings. Establishing a baseline may be done using one of these four primary approaches: stipulation, standardized tables, manufacturer's specifications, and actual measurement.

The most straightforward approach is to stipulate. In fact, it brings about the lowest risk exposure possible for all involved parties. In this approach, prior to the deployment of the baseline, all stakeholders reach an agreement on its parameters. In most cases, engineering calculations and/or judgements serve as the foundation for this agreement. When establishing baselines, it is sometimes helpful to make use of standardized tables that provide a definition of "Default Values".

Information from manufacturers is the third source of data that may be used in the process of constructing baselines. These details may be gathered from the equipment's verified performance records, as well as from its specification papers and test results. The collection of real measurements of the baseline equipment while it is running in the field prior to its removal or alteration as part of the project is the fourth source. This technique of determining baselines has several drawbacks, the most significant of which are the length of time it takes and the amount of money it costs regarding its deployment. In most cases, longer time periods are necessary for the process of data collecting due to unexpected performance scenarios. Because of this, the overall cost to carry out the project will, of course, go up.

If the baseline is determined by actual measurement, it is often derived from data that was measured over a period—a period before the intervention—and then it is adjusted to account for the weather and/or other factors that were prevalent at that time. The duration of that period should be flexible; depending on the building, if the baseline period is less than one year, the data can be extrapolated to construct a full-year baseline period; however, to consider, the changing of the seasons, it is generally recommended that the period be at least one year long.

6.3 Savings evaluation

The amount of savings or benefits reached by the measures adopted is calculated as the difference between the actual performance and the baseline scenario and can always be reasonably forecasted based on the system engineers' calculation and experience. Accuracy of the estimated performance is dependent upon historical data, variances of natural conditions, and empirical estimation.

A good estimation of the performance is fundamental to make a correct evaluation of economic indices, such as the net present value (NPV) and the payback period, and then to determine some parameters of the payment structure in the contract. But differences frequently occur between the estimated and the realized savings amount according to the facilities' nature. In fact, savings and benefits are subjected to uncertainties that stem from multiple factors. Some factors can be assessed and corrected to acceptable levels through the measurement and verification process, such as, for example for energy savings, the outdoor temperature, the occupancy, and the production levels. But, some factors, such as the energy price, cannot be measured and might evolve over the contracting period randomly, these factors are more difficult to consider both for the estimation and for the correction of savings.

As already said a standard evaluation of savings throughout the term of the contract doesn't exist, but some good practices have been developed, such as those documented in IPMVP. Since the latter one is the most used protocol, an overview of the different IPMVP options is presented below **[16]**.

- Option A: The amount of money saved is calculated based on measurements taken in the field of the key parameter(s) that define the amount of energy an isolated refit of a device consumes and the demand it places on the grid. The duration of the reporting period as well as the predicted fluctuations in the parameters that are being monitored determine the range of measurement frequency, which may be anywhere from short-term to continuous.
- Option B: Savings are estimated by field measurement of the energy consumption and demand and/or associated independent or proxy variables of energy efficiency retrofits. This is the most accurate method for determining savings. The projected fluctuations in savings and the duration of the reporting period both have an impact on the frequency of measurement, which may vary anywhere from short-term to continuous.
- Choice C: The amount of money saved may be ascertained by assessing the total demand and consumption of energy at the meter level for the whole facility or utility. Across the whole of the reporting period, consumption, and demand of energy throughout the entire facility are subjected to continuous measurements.
- Option D: Savings are found by simulating the energy consumption and demand of either the whole facility or a sub-facility. This may be done to establish the overall savings. It has been proved that some simulation algorithms can properly simulate the real energy performance of the plant. This alternative calls for a significant level of expertise in calibrated simulation.

6.4 Payment structure

A key element of the performance contracting schemes is the design of payment flows, agreements, and processes between all the actors involved, i.e., the payment structure, with the identification of the beneficiaries of the payments and the reward structure, and the duration of the contract **[12]**.

The way payments are made is an essential component of the overall design of the program, and how they are made is dependent on the performance contracting model that is used. In some instances, consumers cash in their savings and rewards directly, while in other instances, incentive payments are paid to an implementer or aggregator, or they are shared between the two parties. In other instances, customers cash in their savings and prizes directly.

The time of the pay-out is another aspect that distinguishes the payment structure from other similar systems. In many instances, an initial payment is offered to the program implementer, or an upfront

incentive is given to the client after the installation of the measure has been certified. Subsequently, many performance-based payments are made for savings that have been measured and verified. It is feasible to alleviate implementers or consumers of part of the initial cost load of the actions that are adopted by using this method. Another methods foundation incentive pay-outs exclusively on performance and do not provide any up-front payments at all.

In addition, certain programs include bonuses and/or penalties in the contracts: bonuses serve as additional incentives for greater savings or higher performance, and penalties are refunds that implementers are required to pay if the verified savings or performance are lower than those contracted for the program (as in the case of EPC guaranteed saving model).

The technique of financing an investment that is employed the most often is one in which the investor uses his own financial resources or obtains a loan from the bank for up to 70–80 percentage points of the investment's worth to fund the project. ESCOs are firms that are prepared to invest in projects that have the goal of lowering energy usage and associated expenses. These companies have a strong technical and financial background.

The primary distinction is made according to the way investment projects are carried out, which may be broken down as follows:

BOO (Build - Operate - Own): There is the permanent involvement of the ESCO from the investment phase to the permanent operation and possession of the completed investment (for example, built facility or installed equipment), this system boils down to the purchase of a specific energy service by the investor, for example ensuring that the room is maintained at the appropriate temperature.

BOT (Build - Operate - Transfer): Following the completion of the construction of the ESCO, the investment is used for the first period, and then it is handed over to the investor.

BOOT (Build-Own-Operate-Transfer): This is quite like BOT; however, the service life is increased, and it is a mixture of the first two kinds (BOT and BOOT).

There are four primary categories of EPC contracts, each of which differs from the others in terms of the manner of financing, the allocation of risks between the ESCO and the customer, and the profits derived from the investment that is carried out:

Contracts in which ESCO provides financing while also providing the customer with a promise of cost savings (thus it bears almost the entire investment risk).

Contracts in which the customer or property owner is liable for financing, but the energy services company (ESCO) promises cost reductions on energy use (the risk is divided between the parties to the contract).

Agreements that provide for the full assignment of savings attributable to decreased energy costs by ESCOs, up to the full repayment of the investment.

Contracts for the management of energy, based on which an energy services company (ESCO) is paid for the supply of an energy service.

Figure 16: Example of profit distribution in an EPC.

6.5 Energy savings guarantee designing in EPC

The designing of guarantees in EPC deserves special attention, as it is a key element of EPC, that is one of the most common performance-based contracting models. Indeed, in the past two decades, the EPC market has shown a remarkable growth trend matched with the incremental energy demand and potential for energy and other efficiencies [16].

A standard procedure for the energy cost savings guarantee designing is absent, for this reason it is important to evaluate according to the cases which are the components to be taken into consideration, the benchmarks to be evaluated and how to measure them over time.

As described above, two common payment models in EPC are the **Guaranteed Savings Model** and the **Shared Saving Model**. Comparing the two methods, it appears that GSM, specifying a certain amount of guaranteed energy savings, is preferable by the client, as the risks of failing the set objectives fall on the ESCOs. For this reason, a correct determination of the guaranteed savings can be fundamental for the Company and for this reason mixed contracts are often used, with precautionary guaranteed savings and a subdivision of the excess profit in the event of overperformance. Though EPC shares the basic features of general performance-based contracting, such as long contracting period and performance uncertainties, the cost savings guarantee of EPC has its specialty on the risk valuation and allocation structure. For instance, one of the specialties in EPC is the future cost savings estimation, which involves the uncertainties both from the energy price and the amount of energy savings. Also, the profit-sharing beliefs between the owner and the ESCO are different from general performance-based contracting, especially when there is exceedance beyond the guarantee.

Assuming that there are no additional investments during contracting period, the realized project profit equals the realized cost savings minus the project cost:

$$\text{Realized profit} = \text{Realized cost savings} - \text{Project cost}$$

Project cost is assumed fixed, with a one-time expenditure made at the beginning of the contracting period. The original expected project profit equals the guaranteed cost savings minus the one-time project cost: **Expected profit = Guaranteed cost savings - Project cost**

The profit difference is defined as follows, since project cost is the same:

Profit difference = realized profit - expected profit = realized cost savings - guaranteed cost savings

If the realized energy savings over-perform beyond the guarantee, realized cost savings > Guaranteed cost savings, then the Profit difference would be positive, and the owner and the ESCO may share the exceeding part with a certain percentage.

The process for determining the guaranteed savings can be summarized in 4 phases:

- Collection of data related to the project, such as energy price, historic energy consumptions, weather data
- Energy savings estimate, performed through models that take in account variables such as future energy price and that are estimate for every year of the life cycle of the project
- Define profit sharing risks between client and the ESCO
- Determine ideal guarantee parameters, including cost savings and overachieving shared percentage.

6.6 Contract duration

The length of the contract period has a significant impact on the risks allocation and benefits sharing, since it directly affects the interests and risks of both the involved parties. A reasonable length of the contract period can help to alleviate the financial risk for both the contractor and the owner, so that they could reach their expected investment returns within the operation period [15].

Long contract periods encourage deeper savings since more measures with longer payback periods can be implemented and then more profit can be made over time. Nevertheless, contracts with a long duration can discourage implementers because they must manage risks for a longer period. Furthermore, customers generally want to shorten the contract period to a reasonable length, to guarantee their project rights and interests after the well-equipped facility transferred. So, the contract length is selected after balancing the interests of both the customers and the implementers [13].

In general, many challenges and problems have been encountered which affect satisfied performance achievement due to the uncertainties and unforeseen risks over a long contract period, typically more than 10 years. So, the determination of the contract length becomes a critical issue in the negotiations between the owners and the implementers, but it is a complex problem, due to its subjectivity, non-linearity, and multi-criteria features.

To solve this problem, scholars adopted various research methods, such as the net present value (NPV), the payback period, the NPV-at-risk method, NPV-based concession models, bargaining-game theory, and simulation techniques. As one of the commonly used investment evaluation methods, the NPV-at-risk method is formed by the combination of the weighted average cost of capital and dual risk-return methods. Compared with the traditional NPV method, the NPV-at-risk method requires the probability distributions of variables, whereas those are hard to evaluate. Hence, this method is useful in assisting relatively simple decision-making in the investment evaluation for privately financed infrastructure projects. The uncertain factors are most likely to alter the project performance and future cash flow within the contract period. To address the inevitable uncertainties, the simulation modelling approach provides a powerful tool for stochastic modelling process and risk allocation in uncertain environments. Simulation is the imitation of the operation of a real-world process or system over time and can be used to measure and evaluate construction and economic uncertainties and risks.

Regarding EPC, the determination methods can provide valuable references for a possible way of solving the contract period problem, however, few studies have investigated the problem on the determination

of the contract period length in EPC. Currently, the contract periods in EPC are mostly determined based on empirical estimation, rather than quantitative analysis. Thus, the outcomes might differ significantly from the verified performance which may not be the baseline condition signed in the contract. Length of performance-based contracts can vary between one and twenty years.

7 Analysis of opportunities and barriers

In this chapter a brief analysis of advantages/disadvantages of performance contracting against traditional financial schemes and their main barriers and risks and promising opportunities is conducted.

7.1 Comparison with traditional financial programmes

Traditional financial programs compute, or assess in advance, the anticipated performance or quantity of savings during the lifespan of each measure based on pre-specified unit saving values. However, these estimations lack standardization are prone to parameter mistakes, and disregard rebound effects. In addition, the structure of their payments, which often consists of offering clients a one-time upfront reward, makes it difficult to both inspire and monitor persistent success. These technological and market gaps are addressed by new business models such as EPC and P4P, which centre their attention on the performances that are obtained by the measures implemented and, as a result, reduce the risk of underperformance. Customers are better able to determine the actual cost of attaining the outcomes they seek when contracts are based on performance. To put it more simply, it demands the customer to re-evaluate the goals and objectives that need to be addressed, as well as to go via a structured management method to engage a provider that will satisfy those requirements at the lowest overall cost and deliver the most value to the business [18].

In addition, the client is not responsible for the performance risk since the performance contracting concept and its payment structure transfer the responsibility for that risk to the implementers, who are thus compensated at a slightly higher rate. Performance-based contracting raises the likelihood that the working relationship between the customer and the contractor will be better than in traditional contractual arrangements, and that the quality of service will be higher as a result of the improved relationship as a result of the raised likelihood that the working relationship will be better than in traditional contractual arrangements. This is due, in part, to the fact that parties involved in performance-based contractual arrangements are more inclined to regard one another as partners rather than as opponents [18].

Although there is little to no risk involved for the client, performance contracting models are still not widely used because there is a lack of awareness of these programs. Additionally, because the payback period may be longer, it is unclear whether they allow for greater cost savings or improved performance at lower costs than traditional models. Key elements of performance contracting are:

- Choosing an ESCO that has a solid track record, and a positive reputation is one of the most important aspects of performance contracting.
- Commitment from management as well as a comprehension of both the process as a whole and the contract.
- Achievable and agreeable to all parties involved goals and aims.
- A method of effectively resolving issues and problems.

- A procedure of ongoing review during the term of assured cost reductions and improved performance

Good leadership and a capable project team are two of the most important variables that contribute to the accomplishment of the goals set out in a performance contract. In addition of these two factors, readiness on the part of management to accept new challenges and adjust, a productive interaction between the project and its organization, project plan that is unambiguous and has been approved by all parties, and implementable energy management program are important for the success of the performance contraction

7.2 SWOT Analysis

This section provides the results of the SWOT analysis, performed by T2.2 participants in a dedicated workshop session, to reveal the drivers and the barriers during the contracting phase and the implementation of the EPC models.

Figure 17 EPC models SWOT analysis board

The results of this sessions are listed in the tables below.

7.2.1 Shared savings model

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Zero risk” to clients, ESCO assumes the technical and financial risks. • Internationally supported model. • Return balanced investment between the customer and the ESCO. • ESCOs sign a financing and performance contract. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Contracting is limited to cost-effective measures. • ESCO: long contracting periods may be required for paybacks (long period dependency). • Project Size dependency.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future legal adequation to new efficiency requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of contracts.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The higher the energy saving and the higher the gain for the CEC and ESCO. • Creation of a relationship between customer and service provider which can lead to the development of further projects. • In CEC, adaptability to a huge variety of projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the CECs: first savings on energy bills relatively low. • Weak technical qualification of personnel. • Defining how to share savings.
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Table 2 Shared Saving model SWOT analysis.

7.2.2 Guaranteed saving model

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CECs which are based on self-investments can integrate this scheme easier. • Contractor will guarantee in an addendum to the original agreement that it is committed to reimburse any stated savings not achieved. • ESCO may facilitate third party financing mechanisms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Contracting is limited to cost-effective measures. • Financial risk for the loan that CEC should require • For the CEC: the ESCOs design and implement the EPC project but does not finance it. • Determinate the reason that could make to lose saving and if it's a technical risk of the ESCO (terms for each contract).
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In CEC, adaptability to a huge variety of projects. • Future legal adequation to new efficiency requirements. • Fuel pricing leads suitable structure. <p>Sustainable financial instrument opportunities (for example, green mortgages, crowdfunding...)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of contracts. • Weak technical qualification of personnel. • Efficiency, Cost optimization, comfort balance could be not easy to achieve. • Capacity of the ESCO to refund the CEC to repay the debt. • Definition of the baseline. • Volatility of the energy market. • Customers must bear upfront capital costs. • It's also necessary to consider an amortization period for the initial investment.

Table 3 Guaranteed Savings model SWOT analysis.

7.2.3 Chauffage model

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The customer will instantly lower their costs since the fixed fee will be lower than what they are paying currently. • ESCOs are encouraged to improve their technology (optimization, MPC, AI...). • For the CEC: technical risk and financial are guaranteed by the ESCO (pay bill, maintenance, upgrades, interventions). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for economic and legal knowledge to identify the investors. • Complex pre contracting phase. • A strength is the lower requirement for customer involvement, but this can also be seen as a weakness. • Less saving than the other models: energy to its customer at a certain discounted rate and meeting.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is not the same need for an energy baseline to compare with since there is no savings guarantee. • It doesn't rely on single heavy investments from the customer, and this makes the projects easier to realize from a financing perspective. • Suitable for renovation and management of energy systems in buildings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of customer's engagement related to the intervention. • Efficiency, Cost optimization, comfort balance is specially not easy to achieve. • The customer side incentive to save energy is a bit weaker compared to other contracting forms.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of cutting-edge technologies could be easier. • Fuel pricing leads suitable structure. • Future legal adequation to new efficiency requirements. • May lead to hybrid models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak technical qualification of personnel. • Complexity of technical aspects for the CEC (clients) to verify the system. • Savings report discrepancies. • The lack of participation from customer's side makes this scheme fully dependent on ESCOs services and outsourcing. ESCO can take the advantage of it.

Table 4 Chauffage model SWOT analysis.

An additional comparison between guaranteed and shared saving has been performed:

Guaranteed savings	Shared Savings
Performance related to level of energy saved	Performance related to cost of energy saved; the ESCO bills upon actual results
Value of energy saved is guaranteed to meet debt service obligations down to a floor price	Value of payments to ESCO is linked to energy price; betting on price of energy can be risky
ESCO carries performance risk	ESCO carries performance and credit risk as it typically carries out the financing
Energy-user/customer carries credit risk	Usually off the balance sheet of energy-user/customer
If the energy-user/customer borrows, then debt appears on its balance sheet	Can serve customers that do not have access to financing
Requires creditworthy customer	Equipment may be leased
Extensive M&V	Favours large ESCOs; small ESCOs become too leveraged to do more projects
More comprehensive	How to share the 'excess' savings

¹Table 5 Guaranteed Savings and Shared Saving models comparison (Dreessen 2003 / Poole 2003).

¹ Data source: Dreessen 2003 [21], and Poole and Stoner 2003 [22].

7.3 Main barriers

The performance contracting market is still in the process of evolving, but it is not particularly popular just now since there are various restrictions that hinder it from spreading. The most significant obstacles are discussed in more detail below [7].

- An insufficient amount of awareness and experience. Convincing consumers, developing performance contracts, and arranging the financing may be challenging endeavours due to the widespread lack of familiarity with performance-based contracting and the mechanism used to finance it [19].
- The difficulty of establishing and reaching an agreement on a baseline to use as a point of reference for estimating cost reductions or increases in performance [20]. Performance is impacted by shifts in variables, such as fluctuations in the cost of energy, the state of the weather, and the behaviour of individuals, all of which are difficult to anticipate [12]. Therefore, before entering performance contracting, the measurement and verification technique, also known as M&V, must be agreed upon. However, acceptable revisions or adjustments should also be permitted since things may change over the course of years. The adoption of EPC and P4P [19] has been hampered because of the difficulty of accurately evaluating performance, such as the energy performance of buildings or the effectiveness of demand response activities, as well as the absence of universally acknowledged criteria for calculating savings. In addition, the measurement and verification activities need an effort that is both complicated and possibly costly.
- Complex legal and contractual difficulties. Performance contracts are one-of-a-kind documents that are based on intricate and intricate transactions. These transactions include the methods of contract performance as well as the methodology for measuring savings and calculating payments. Performance contracts are characterized by their uniqueness and complexity. Implementers and prospective customers frequently have a difficult time deciding on the terms of the contract and understanding their roles, obligations, and the distribution of risks [19].
- It is believed that key potential impediments to effective performance contracting include a lack of commitment to the implementers at all levels of the organization as well as trust between the parties (the client and the implementer) [20].
- Performance contracting may not be a good fit for small businesses because it can be more expensive and complicated to obtain cost savings, which can result in longer payback periods that hinder their diffusion [12].
- In particular, there are certain circumstances in which performance contracting may not be appropriate. There are several obstacles that should be overcome before a widespread implementation of the EPC concept in residential structures. The obstacles are the following [9]:
 - The disproportionately high transaction costs for energy efficiency service providers in comparison to the relatively low cost of energy and the potential reduction in cost for each individual energy efficiency service provided.
 - The significant degree of fragmentation that exists within the mass market as well as the need to analyse each of the elements involved into the financial structure independently. Because of this, it is challenging to provide energy efficiency services that are standardized. This barrier could seem to be especially pertinent in the context of Citizen Energy Communities, which are made up of individuals from a variety of backgrounds.
 - The so-called landlord-tenant conundrum is caused by the fact that although the tenant generally has an interest in achieving energy savings through energy efficiency improvement actions, the landlord typically receives no benefits from these investments or can barely pass on investment costs to the tenant. This creates a situation in which the landlord is faced with a dilemma known as the landlord-tenant conundrum.

- The legal requirement that exists in some countries and stipulates that for a landlord of a multifamily building to be permitted to pass on the costs of energy efficiency improvement action investments to tenants, all the tenants in the building must first agree to make these investments.
- The privatization of apartment complexes and other multi-unit structures (which usually represent the most interesting investments for energy efficiency service suppliers and financiers). This approach has, in many circumstances, resulted in real estate situations in which each apartment in a building has a distinct owner. Because of this, choices about the building shell and building technology have become increasingly difficult to make. In each nation, the procedures for making decisions are structured differently. In most cases, the approval of at least one half or possibly all of the apartment owners are necessary before a renovation may take place.
- The fact that the individual requirements and behaviours of residents have a significantly stronger influence on the amount of energy used in the residential sector than they do in other sectors. Because of this, it may be very challenging to determine a consumption baseline, and it can lead to significant risks when attempting to provide energy savings assurances. In addition, individual energy consumption meters for heat and hot water are frequently absent in multi-family apartment complexes, which makes it difficult for single-family homes to make judgments on investments in energy efficiency.
- Difficulty for potential customers to get oriented among the existing energy efficiency service offers because of the lack of information on the available offers and services and the difficulty in understanding the EPC concept. This is due to both the lack of information on the available offers and services and the difficulty in understanding the EPC concept.
- A lack of confidence on the part of service providers for energy efficiency as a result of the absent regulatory framework for their certification and the negative experiences that some households have had.
- The worry that one will become overly dependent on the energy efficiency service contractor, as well as the possibility that the service provided will be more expensive in comparison to, for example, the scenario in which the provider is not (partially) paid by the energy savings achieved by the organization.
- The economic crisis and the current geopolitical events both contribute to the political and economic uncertainty.
- The scarce or difficult accessibility of public subsidies and financing capital for energy efficiency service implementation.

7.4 Risk identification and allocation

Through the use of an integrated acquisition and logistics process, the performance-based contracting technique may purchase performance, which ultimately results in an increased capacity across a variety of goods and services. Long contractual periods and a significant number of numerous uncertainties are, in most cases, the primary causes for worry over retrofit risks in these types of projects. In performance-based projects, contractual guarantees are often used as a strategy for addressing the many risks that are inherent in the predetermined contracting duration. Valuation approaches for risk assets give sophisticated tools for stochastic modeling and risk estimations, which are necessary in order to quantify the uncertainties and come to the proper conclusions about guarantees. The **NPV-at-risk method, the real option method, and the simulation method** are the three primary methods that make up contemporary approaches to risk valuation. When dealing with the trade-offs of contracting conflict and cooperation

amongst rational decision-makers, risk appraisal and risk allocation are two important issues that need to be addressed. Both issues are crucial in their own right [16].

In the research that has been done, several risk classifications have been offered, and some of the categories into which hazards may be divided are as follows:

- Economic risks are the probable losses that might occur because of fluctuations in the prices of things like energy costs, demand charges, material costs, equipment costs, and labor expenses. The majority of the standard forms of P4P or EPC contracts include a clause that stipulates that both parties to the contract are responsible for the risk of variations in energy costs and demand charges, and that the baseline of those costs will be adjusted accordingly whenever such variations take place. This clause is relevant because it stipulates that both parties bear the risk of variations in energy costs and demand charges. It is usual practice for the implementer to take complete responsibility for the risks associated with increases in material prices, equipment costs, and labor expenses. These risks might arise from fluctuations in material costs, equipment costs, or labor costs.
- Risks associated with finances: in general, there are two major forms of funding, which are self-financing, and financing obtained from a third party. When using the first method, the host is the one who pays the initial capital cost for the implementation of the project. However, in certain EPC models, the ESCO is the one who assumes the performance risk by providing a guarantee on the amount of energy savings that will be achieved using the proposed ECMs. The second option allows the ESCO or the host to apply for a loan from a financial institution that is not affiliated with either side. It is possible that the financial institution will seek a guarantee from the ESCO about the potential energy savings to secure the capacity to make repayments.
- Risks associated with the design of the project: For performance-based initiatives, having an accurate calculation of the savings is essential to their overall success. The availability of operational data, which is used to estimate performances for the newly implemented measures, is vital for the implementers to assess the project risk of predicted savings. This is important for the implementers to do even if a suitable engineering design has been developed.
- Risks Associated with Installation: P4P and EPC projects sometimes require the removal of pre-existing equipment and the installation of new equipment in buildings that are already in use. Work on the removal and installation is only permitted during certain hours to reduce the amount of inconvenience caused to the inhabitants. Because of this, the completion of the project may be delayed, which will also cause a lag in the realization of the actual savings.
- Inaccurate sizing, inappropriate system selection, and unanticipated degradation are all examples of what are referred to as "technology risks." These risks may create variances in the performance and longevity of the equipment. In most cases, the implementer is entirely responsible for bearing any technological risks that may arise throughout the term of the contract.
- Modifications in the specified operating schedule and control strategy of the newly installed equipment are the cause of operational hazards, which have been linked to these changes. In actuality, the parties to the contract will often engage in negotiations on the distribution of operational risks. When it comes to performance-based contracts, most of the time, the implementers are not held accountable for any deficit in savings that may occur as a result of the host failing to run the system in accordance with the agreed-upon control strategy and processes. The actual performances might also be affected by other linked hazards, such as the unpredictability of the weather and the occupancy levels. Although contracts often include an adjustment mechanism to handle the effect coming from changes in baseline, it is very difficult to evaluate these affects, resulting in uncertainty in real savings. This is despite the fact that contracts typically include an adjustment mechanism.

- Modeling mistakes, inadequate data quality for M&V tasks, and imprecise measurements are some of the potential dangers associated with measurement and verification. All of these dangers are inherently present, and both parties need to share the responsibility for mitigating them.

7.5 Promising opportunities in the energy sector

Performance contracting models offer the ability to involve the private sector in increasing expenditures and savings in energy efficiency, hence reducing consumptions and CO₂ emissions or enhancing demand response activities. It's possible that private investors and businesses have more leeway to experiment and be willing to take on performance risk than utilities must stimulate innovation in energy efficiency. P4P and EPC programs can be helpful in assessing savings and motivating persistence in savings from complex, multi-measure efficiency projects, such as those with behavioural or operational changes, where it is difficult to deem savings in advance. P4P and EPC programs can also help in the case where it is difficult to deem savings in advance.

Performance contracting presents several prospects beyond the enhancement of energy innovation, the development of green jobs, and the change of the market, including the following:

- Energy communities might be a new area of application for pay-for-performance and energy performance contracting (P4P and EPC), given that performance contracts are more likely to be effective when targeted at aggregators rather than individual consumers. The consolidation of several buildings into a single entity enhances the precision of the baseline and savings estimations and makes it possible to put into action efficiency measures that result in higher performance at reduced expense.
- Standardizing measuring techniques may help cut costs for aggregators and other implementers, as well as guarantee that efficiency savings are reported in a consistent and transparent manner by all parties involved.
- The performance contracting concept has not been very popular in the residential sector so far, possibly because measuring methodologies have been too expensive to scale up this point. The residential sector is the new frontier for P4P or EPC programs. More sophisticated EM&V processes are worth it for implementers if they have large clients and the potential to save a lot of money. However, as the use of smart meters becomes more widespread, the process of collecting data on energy consumption will become less complicated, and the cost of measurements that encompass the entire building will decrease. This will make the measurement procedures, which are necessary for the success of such a program, more practical for residential and small commercial buildings.

P4P programs may target a variety of indicators, including behavioural and operational measurements, as well as technological measures. This methodology is often used to guarantee that savings are realized.

7.6 CEC requirements

Energy performance contracting offers several features that address the concerns of many CEC actors, with the increased need to optimize their energy usage, while lacking at time the necessary funding, expertise, or resources. Making the CEC buildings to consume less energy is not a simple task, the analysis is a complex and requires a certain level of detail.

To be able to adapt the innovative contracting models and ensure that the range of the energy services that will be considered under these contract will fit NEON CECs need and commit to the associated performance with a view to innovation, profitability, simplicity and performance, the following section will address and analyse the CEC requirements expressed via the existing services identification in T1.1 Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes and the preliminary business planning in T1.2 Service offer co-creation and business planning. To provide a concise explanation of the requirements within each NEON CEC, the elaboration will be divided into four main key elements:

- The deployment layout of energy systems,
- The CEC stakeholder’s system (legal framework, charter, ownership, etc.),
- The existence of any energy purchase specific scheme,
- Financial structure (funding, maintenance, etc.).

NEON’s CECs requirements based on the preliminary business plan defined in T1.2 were reported in the tables below.

CEC 01: BERCHIDDA, Berchidda Municipality, Italy

<p>Deployment layout of energy systems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the first e-meters (maybe two types of measure to quantify the energy feed-in the grid) • Determinate which houses will use e-meters to manage the loads. • Integration of the energy storage system.
<p>Stakeholder system</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meters installed will be property of the CEC • Need to determinate the maximum actuation level over the end-user’s comfort • Referral program to increase the interest of new end-users. • Study the legal framework of energy contracts and regulations of each country. • Analyze the regulatory framework for internal contracts with community members.
<p>Existence of any energy purchase specific scheme.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy flow of each member compared to the community. Matrix of prices according to the amount of energy consumed vs the estimated PV energy available to achieve a more correlated consumption with the PV installations. • Existing building energy community it’s a non-technical service, needs to be added to the CEC.
<p>Financial structure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance could pay monthly for each stakeholder and could include some features as PV installation revision.

Table 6 CEC 01” BERCHIDDA” requirements.

CEC 02 : DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE, Villard de Lans, France

<p>Deployment layout of energy systems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of Linky meters on the NEON platform if it's possible and the HP management system. • Integration between the PV installation and the existing services.
<p>Stakeholder system</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An explanation of the energy system of the resort and how it works. • Also, customers could have a fixed prices by have a higher general price. • Study the legal framework of energy contracts and regulations of each country. • Analyse the regulatory framework for internal contracts with community members.
<p>Existence of any energy purchase specific scheme.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The energy used by the customers also need to have a matrix of hours and prices by ToU (Implementation of improvement to the existing). • Existing market to sell the surplus energy produced (Actual price seems to be lower than expected).
<p>Financial structure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPC and P4P to ensure the energy consumed have different prices according to the source where it comes. • The maintenance contracts for the equipment could be the existing ones, adding the fixed priced of the performing process that the CEC will acquire with NEON platform. • The resort works as service provider and energy provider, that's why it's the only member which takes the financial and technical risk.

Table 7 CEC 02 "DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE" requirements.

CEC 03: POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS, Villacañas (Toledo), Spain

<p>Deployment layout of energy systems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-meters integration on the residential buildings and final users. • Creation of the CEC platform. • Integrate all costumers and services information.
<p>Stakeholder system</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meters installed are property of the customer. • Need to determinate the maximum actuation level over the end-user's comfort. • Study the legal framework of energy contracts and regulations of each country. • Analyse the regulatory framework for internal contracts with community members.
<p>Existence of any energy purchase specific scheme.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determinate the price of the batteries depending on when its used and, the penalties (higher prices) for high consumption of end-users during the night.

Financial structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4P and EPC to ensure the energy consumed comes from the renewable sources proposed. • Monthly cost because of taking part of the CEC. • The CEC takes the financial risk of forming the community, the end users of the equipment and the services providers of each installation.
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Table 8 CEC 03 “POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS “requirements.

CEC 04: STAIN City, Stains, FRANCE

Deployment layout of energy systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of whole measures system for the building and each type of technology. • Measured energy storage with different technologies. • Combined electrical and hydrogen production.
Stakeholder system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete ownership of the services and energy provider of ENGIE as being installed in their premises. • Study the legal framework of energy contracts and regulations of each country. • Analyse the regulatory framework for internal contracts with community members.
Existence of any energy purchase specific scheme.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The energy flux of that CEC is a Mix Power Plant with an internal consumption and the feed-in possibility.
Financial structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each neighbour will pay for their own meter to quantify the energy consumed. • Not special contracts need because the energy used by the CEC participants will be only the surplus of the photovoltaic energy locally produced.

Table 9 CEC 04 "STAIN City" requirements.

8 Gaps

8.1 Introduction

There are several energy contracting schemes that can be applied in facilities with energy deployments. However, in the case of energy communities (CECs specifically), there are additional elements to consider. In this section, these particularities that make the requirements for energy communities substantially different from the typical schemes are presented.

The gaps that have been identified have been grouped into different categories. Thus, first, the general problem is addressed through the general divergent aspects that arise between the implementation of the schemes described in the previous sections within the framework of traditional casuistry and their implementation within the structure of citizen energy communities.

Likewise, based on the general gaps, three major specific fields of divergence will be analyzed to identify qualitatively and, if possible, quantitatively the specific action points for the creation of the guideline for the implementation of the contracting schemes described in this document.

First, the legal and administrative aspects will be analyzed. These are the focus of differentiation in the objects of application of the procurement schemes. They are more complicated elements from the statutory and legal point of view, which, in addition, must be adjusted to the legislation in force in the territory of application. They are also the legal basis that will establish fiscal and legal responsibilities and the proprietary aspects of the energy community. In addition to all this, they will also establish the respective administrative procedures that correspond to the actions that will be defined in the following sections for the creation of the guideline for the implementation of the contracting schemes in the energy communities.

The economic and financial aspects are strongly linked to the legal and contractual ones since many of the requirements (participation, rights, and access to financing schemes) depend directly on the administration and the legal framework. In any case, due to the different typologies of legal figures, active agents and participatory and constitutive processes, there are clearly identifiable differentiating elements between the financing and economic structure aspects of traditional implementations and those corresponding to energy communities.

Finally, there are the social factors. In the case of typical contracts in today's energy market, the customer is usually clearly defined as well as his motivation or, on the part of the ESCO, the corresponding commercial action. However, in the case of energy communities, there are several social factors such as lack of knowledge, lack of organization and collective mobilization, complete ignorance of the market, and skepticism. Those factors can be a real barrier to the establishment of standardized procedures for the implementation of energy contracts. In this section, they will be analyzed with the aim of systematically identifying the existing divergences between traditional processes and those corresponding to energy communities to create the optimal implementation methodology lines in citizen energy communities.

8.2 General gaps

As mentioned above, we first analyzed the general divergent aspects between the traditional implementation processes and the requirements of the energy communities. Thus, one of the main general gaps is the need for transformation of passive consumers (citizens, companies, entities) into active subjects of the energy supply value chain. In the case of energy services and their standard contracts, contractual relationships can be established more easily; however, in the case of energy communities, if there is no active participation, it is difficult to create specific agreements and contracts with a legal basis.

In the case of energy communities, another fundamental need is to properly combine top-down and bottom-up support and initiatives in a way that avoids contradictions and impositions. This aspect is of vital importance in the context of the functioning of energy communities since (in general, with few exceptions), unlike pyramidal corporate structures, energy communities are governed by the open participation of their members as well as by non-discriminatory democratic participation. As examples of actions and procedures that should be avoided, in projects in which there has been an attempt to act from above and without a participatory and consensual work with the agents involved in the community, in

which those who should participate have become those affected, the initiatives have had serious difficulties to materialize simple actions. Therefore, in these cases, the capacity to act at the decision-making level in terms of energy services becomes practically null, to the point of possibly leading to the dissolution of the energy community. Therefore, it is essential to create appropriate mechanisms to systematize and integrate open and democratic participation at all levels and for all general cases that may occur in the heart of citizen energy communities.

Another important general factor is the need for adequate incentive and support mechanisms. Once the participatory and constitutive tools have been established, it is essential to generate mechanisms, especially public ones, that facilitate, encourage, and popularize the proliferation, understanding and dissemination of contractual procedures for energy services as citizen energy communities multiply. These mechanisms would lay the foundations for primary sources of information covering the entire process as well as the lessons learned from use cases (with both their positive and negative aspects).

A specific requirement is the creation of clear promotional instruments that are easy to access or apply for energy communities that do not have high technical or legal-administrative capacities or resources and that allow access to the mechanisms described in the previous point. This aspect must also have administrative support and a clear and dynamic dissemination plan.

8.3 Legal and administrative framework

Once the general factors of divergence between traditional implementation structures and those of the energy communities are understood, the legal and administrative factors will be addressed. The first relevant point to analyze is related to the legislation and regulations in force. The legal frameworks corresponding to traditional businesses that are merged into commercial companies are fully regulated in all European countries, so that the legal and administrative aspects corresponding to traditional implementations do not pose any problem. However, in the case of energy communities, there is a non-homogeneous legal vacuum that gives rise to a constant uncertainty and lack of knowledge about the legal and administrative structure of energy communities. Thus, it is necessary to create a coherent legal framework, without contradictions or loopholes, accompanied by a coherent regulatory development. This aspect, in turn, must be closely related to the creation of support mechanisms and dissemination instruments described in the previous section for its proper implementation.

Another important aspect is the procurement of consumption data for the technical procedures required by the contracting schemes. It is essential that there is a framework of transparency and accessibility to the data while respecting the data protection rights of the active agents of the energy community. In other words, it is necessary to ensure the availability of information on real consumption in real time (or almost real -quarterly-) to obtain the maximum benefit for all segments of the value chain of the electricity sector. However, protection and cybersecurity must be integrated and regulated over the individual right to data protection and the legal casuistry that this may entail to the detriment of the implementation of energy contracting schemes. The control of electricity distribution going forward, according to current trends, information is and will be increasingly more important for distributors and marketers than energy itself. This is especially important for the incorporation of stochastic generation that is highly dependent on the ability to absorb energy when it is produced, therefore, controllability of distribution is key. This scheme may seem common in all areas of applicability, however, in energy communities it becomes vitally

important due to the enormous casuistry that can be had in reference to individual contracts with marketers, tariffs, etc.

Finally, it is also essential to promote interoperability understood, in the context of smart metering, as the ability of two or more systems, device applications or components to interact, exchange and use information to facilitate proactive demand management. This involves a complicated legal framework scheme since it is not a company associated to a specific registry but depends on the characteristics of the stakeholders of the energy communities. This is one of the main administrative pitfalls to be defined in the guidelines to be created in this document.

8.4 Economic and financing gaps

General gaps and those related to the legal framework have been described in sections above. This section will address only those related to economic and financial aspects. In the private sector, all implementation activities of energy procurement schemes are based on private investments by the agents involved in the schemes themselves. However, in the case of energy communities, private investment is not as active or as high as one might expect. Thus, one of the main economic gaps is the need to activate private financing. In this aspect, one of the keys is to limit the risks to make attractive financial products available. In the current situation, the greatest risk is perceived in the legal definition of community and the legal recognition of its competences, capacities, and responsibilities.

Closely linked to the previous point is the energy services company concept. This concept is being applied successfully and repeatedly in specific project profiles, such as public lighting, and rather occasionally in projects to improve buildings or industrial processes. Thus, although in the private sector and in public tenders, the definition of ESCOs is very widespread, in the case of energy communities, on numerous occasions, there are often participations of energy companies that are not ESCOs as such but hybrids that operate as facilitators (but do not offer complete engagement or contracting services). Therefore, it is necessary to promote the participation of energy service companies (ESCOs) both from the point of view of the ESCOs themselves and from the point of view of the stakeholders of the energy communities.

As an example, experience shows that contracts related to guaranteed savings are successful when applied to a service where the energy balance is not complex, where the different energy vectors do not interact and, above all, where the consumption pattern is very predictable. As we move away from these ideal conditions, the contracting process becomes more complex and more costly. The high fixed costs condition the minimum size of a project of this type, so ESCOs usually look for projects with a volume of more than 300,000 euros. Therefore, and as mentioned above, apart from the vision of the ESCO, there may be reluctance on the part of the energy community if it is a “distant” company, with no local presence or roots. This is a complicated gap that must be structured in an appropriate way in the guidelines presented in the subsequent sections of this document.

Another aspect that clearly differs from the classic structures is the involvement of the public sectors, with the objective to test and promote collaboration models: public administration + private company + local community = PPCP. This scheme would facilitate the implementation not only of the energy community itself but also of the energy contracting elements.

An external agent that emerges and is not configured in the same way in the classic business sectors as in the energy communities is the " aggregator". Therefore, exploiting the role of the aggregator in the field of citizen energy communities will be a key aspect in the future. The aggregator can be a vehicle for virtual energy communities and/or with the capacity to group several physical and virtual communities, thus laying the foundations for a more favorable framework in the energy negotiation, financing and contracting processes and facilitating the integration of the ESCO figure.

As described in European directives, the benefits related to citizen energy communities are related to environmental, social (such as energy poverty or social cohesion) and economic aspects, unlike most traditional schemes. This aspect allows adding the economic benefits from different sources (reduction of the fixed term of energy, reduction of tolls for a reduced use of the transport network), with the social and environmental benefits perceived by the local community, such as the creation of jobs at local level, the fight against energy poverty, the improvement of air quality at local level or the increase of house comfort. Obviously, these aspects make the contracting structures more complex and modify the dynamics with the ESCOs, but it is an essential gap to incorporate in the implementation guidelines.

Also, related to the previous point, it is necessary to identify "quick wins". Through them, it is possible to obtain the first successes relatively quickly and encourage new initiatives to take shape, not only in terms of energy service structures but also in the creation of communities themselves. Quick win opportunities are unlikely to be found in the energy renovation of buildings or in technologically complex projects, so this is an ideal framework for achieving these factors. Likewise, this activity will promote the integration of the ESCOs in the financial structure of the energy communities, giving rise to an open and competitive market where the rules of the game established by the current market will determine the dynamics described above. This framework also allows the motivation of an integrated action combining incentives for this profile of more complex projects, which would bear fruit in the longer term, with lines focused on "quick wins" type projects. This aspect can lead to a scaling of energy service structures that really bring added value to energy communities.

Unlike large commercial and industrial facilities where achieving scale factor benefits is a priority but a clear and defined structure is involved, in the case of energy communities it can be considerably more complicated. The costs of different equipment, mainly those related to photovoltaic installations, but also those related to energy efficiency interventions, are becoming lower and lower. An effort in purchasing management can keep costs under control and improve profitability as well as compliance with the basic principles of the energy community.

In large facilities, the search for mechanisms to encourage energy renovation can be simpler and even more so with specific schemes such as the "Chauffage". However, the financial structures of energy communities complicate such a scheme and in addition, in these cases, energy refurbishment provides modest economic savings, and the payback period is usually very long. So, there is a considerable gap in the promotion of energy renovation that needs to be addressed for its implementation at least at a theoretical level.

Closing the financial gaps means clarifying the role of parties involved in multi-services energy projects, identifying costs, revenue streams, risk distribution and responsibilities. As mentioned above, there exists a general lack of knowledge – and experience as well – in the direct involvement of Citizen Energy Communities in cross sectoral interventions regarding renewable energy sources, energy efficiency and

smart building interventions. Upcoming Deliverables of Neon project will identify the most feasible financial structures to maximize the efficiency of the service offer, optimizing costs and benefits for all the parties involved: citizens, grid stakeholders, service providers.

8.5 Social gaps

The social gaps that exist when considering the implementation of energy service contracting schemes in the framework of citizen energy communities have been analyzed in comparison to the implementation processes of the schemes in classical casuistries.

In the case of such traditional schemes that have been commented, the basis of the schemes to be implemented is directly focused on the commercial interests of both customers and ESCOs. Lacking participatory processes and having a pyramidal and hierarchical structure based on capitalization and monetization interests (with some few exceptions) allows an executive decision making that only depends on the management and ownership of the facilities. Likewise, a fully defined legal, juridical, and administrative structure favors such a scheme. However, in the case of energy communities, being citizen processes (private and/or public) of open and voluntary participation, it is necessary to focus on the citizen. It becomes essential to build a favorable environment that provides legal certainty, stability and, ultimately, confidence to citizens willing to contribute to the implementation of energy service contracting with their respective schemes and with the integration of the participation of ESCOs.

In traditional schemes, trust is based solely on the customer's capabilities and understanding as well as on their knowledge of the market and the active energy service alternatives present in the current market as well as on the technical and commercial capabilities of the ESCOs. However, in the case of energy communities, trust as a broad and relatively abstract concept in the community structure has to be built. Trust is one of the main values of energy communities. It is precisely the local component that plays an important role here. In valuing local status, people have the need to belong to a group, with identity and a sense of community, with the possibility of self-expression and self-realization, of exchange and solidarity, and of creating or enhancing a certain lifestyle with shared values. From here it is possible to introduce behavioral changes in energy use patterns and in the perception of integration of energy services through contracting schemes such as those described in this document.

Likewise, it is necessary to encourage participation and motivate volunteerism and community self-esteem. Participation in general, and volunteering, are the main drivers of the development of energy communities in different European countries. This activity represents a considerable gap with respect to traditional implementation schemes which do not require participatory processes and active dynamizations.

Another aspect that represents a significant gap with respect to classical structures is the need for communication. In these, the need for communication is centered between the client and the ESCOs within the framework of the definition of the negotiation and implementation processes of the energy service contracts. However, in energy communities, the need for efficient and effective communication is paramount not only with respect to ESCOs but also internally. By effective communication we mean that the information reaches the receiver, who understands, interprets, and internalizes it. For communication to be effective, the receiver must have two-way communication channels with the sender. In this sense,

all communication tools must enable communication channels with the addressee, which in this case is made up primarily of all the stakeholders of the communities and secondly of the relationships with all the external service providers. Thus, within the framework of communication requirements, a good combination of technological and social factors must be established. Technological factors have a dominant global component while social factors are predominantly local. In traditional schemes only the technical aspects are addressed and not always extensively. In energy communities, such a combination is vital.

9 EPC adaptation and the Implementation guidelines

9.1 Social-cultural and operational aspects

Before implementing any contractual scheme in a CEC system, a socio-cultural and socio-economic analysis of the viability of this type of contract in the citizen energy communities to be studied must be carried out. This study will be based on the requirements defined in the previous point and will establish, first, the decision methodology for the implementation of schemes that have been described in this document.

The steps to be followed are as follows:

1. First, the spectrum of potential stakeholders in the CEC has to be analysed. At this point, a distinction must be made between communities that have already been created and those that have not yet been created. In the case of those already created, the coordination action will fall on the legal figure of the community as well as on the promoter (in general ESCOs or any other type of service company, local promotion offices, etc.). In these communities already created, the study will be relatively simple since the stakeholders will be able, under the premises of data protection, to provide all the necessary information for the evaluation. In the case of communities that haven't already been created or are in the process of being created, the aspects to be analysed are various and will be described below. In any case, in the case of the latter, the ER defined in deliverable D6.4 can be applied in reference to Task 1.4 of WP1 of the NEON project.

The following data should be obtained either in the already created CEC or in those that are in the process of being created or not yet created:

- Age ranges included in the stakeholders. This data will help to understand the training and dissemination criteria necessary for the implementation of the schemes.
- Income ranges: these elements are not at all negligible since they are part of the determining factors in the establishment of the contracting conditions.
- Energy system usage habits: these habits (both residential and industrial) will define the deployment and operation actions.
- Consumption and generation systems: clustered consumption and generation systems will be defined. This also includes the network of suppliers and the tariffs associated with each stakeholder.
- Urban economy: another essential aspect is the presence and active part of the urban economy in the CEC and that they are part of the intrinsic economic activity.
- Participation of public facilitators and investors: the presence and level of involvement and participation of public elements, investors or individual producers should also be considered.

The second step is the analysis of the CEC's environment (or its real potential if it is not established) from the point of view of its financial potential. In this aspect, it is important to dimension the investment, credit, and debt capacity of the stakeholders and how their corresponding participation is established, as well as the technical capacities and needs of the CEC.

Finally, the participation and terms of action of both investors and facilitators will also be analysed. Therefore, the following aspects should be considered:

- Technical necessity of the CEC as a whole and the active modifications it may undergo in the future. Technical aspects of consumption and habits collected in the previous step are also included.
- Financial capacity of the CEC: this point will be fully covered in the following sections of the document, but it is important to emphasize the need to define the financial capacity of the CEC.
- System financing options. This scheme can have several sources (private investors, crowdfunding, collective loans, public investment, private producers, etc.) and are very subject to the legislative frameworks of each autonomous territory.
- It is also essential to define the terms of financial responsibility and risk minimization mechanisms (e.g., for non-payment to financial institutions).

Once both the engagement aspects and the technical-economic feasibility aspects have been established, the most suitable schemes should be defined for those CECs where their implementation is appropriate.

The last point is the establishment of the definition of the implementation process of the contracting scheme, where the following points will be univocally defined:

- Technical characteristics of the deployment.
- Necessity of contracting a specific company.
- Selected financing framework and terms of credit responsibility of each of the CEC's stakeholders.
- Procurement procedure (either public by tender or private, depending on the characteristics of the CEC stakeholders) and evaluation criteria of the alternatives.
- Definition of the operating framework.

9.2 ESCOs

Another fundamental aspect is the definition of the participation of ESCOs as specific companies providing energy efficiency services in the CECs. The choice of such a company has numerous advantages, such as those listed below:

- They know the specific technical aspects of efficiency in all environments of human activity.
- They have tools (software and hardware) that can lead to much more precise and controlled energy efficiency actions.
- On the other hand, they have financing and investment capacity, so the proposed schemes can be interesting.
- Finally, they know the specific market, so the results and proposals made both individually by CEC and in a clustered way will be more competitive.

However, each case of CEC requires an evaluation system on the need to implement the services of an ESCO. For them, the following specifications will be considered:

- Specific efficiency management needs: First, before taking any step, and based all the premise on the global criteria discussed in the previous section, the real need and feasibility of the CEC to implement an efficiency management system will be analysed. This aspect will be based mainly on economic factors and on the principles defined in the CEC statutes. It is also possible that this action may require a specific methodology to be implemented in the co-creation processes of the CEC.
- Existence of internal capacity for efficiency management. Based on the previous sociological study and the KPI principles of the characteristics it yields, the need for implementation of professional services or not of an ESCO will be analysed. This point is also based on another fundamental pillar, which is technical capacity.
- Contracting capacity: if the contracting of an ESCO is viable and positive under the premises established in the previous section, the company's services will be contracted based on the established financing and credit responsibility specification factors.

9.3 Baseline, M&V, and payment system adaptation to CECs

If an ESCO services' contract is chosen, it is essential to know the elements for defining the load and its baseline, as well as the verification and measurement elements that will be established with the ESCO for the evaluation of the operation.

1- Baseline. This aspect is of vital importance since it will establish the horizon of comparison without the performance of energy services without the ESCO. The energy baseline is the holy grail of energy efficiency projects. It is a statistical energy model of what the current consumption of a facility should look like if no energy efficiency changes were made. The idea is powerful. If it can be estimated how much energy should the sink consume today, it shall be compared to the energy consumed today and the difference is the savings.

Figure 18 . The statistical energy baselines.

It seems that calculating an energy baseline is straightforward, however, it is not. A baseline is constructed using historical data, typically 12 to 36 months. Facility conditions change a lot over 3 years. For example, the weather may be warmer from one year to the next; or activity may change; or a pandemic may force a building to close for a given period or reduce the number of users (and thus energy consumption) for long periods. Therefore, the baseline statistical model should include parameters that correlate with the facility's energy consumption, if they can be measured, such as outdoor temperature and occupancy

levels. Thus, there is even a protocol for calculating baselines, called the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP).

Another fundamental aspect is the different exposure to climate risks, differentiating between chronic and acute climate hazards, that may differently affect different geographical regions. However, in the case of the systems related to the CEC, the baseline can be easily defined using conventional commercial office tools since they do not require complex operating systems with state variables. If necessary, specific modelling resources should be used.

2- Measurement and verification systems. In this case, in most CEC systems, the installation of metering systems will be required, both for static installation and non-permanent installation such as those shown in the Figure 19.

Figure 19: Local metering equipment (ourtesy of Carlo Gavazzi).

For the implementation of the measurement and verification systems, the economic feasibility study factors will be required as a basis and the specific needs of comparison according to the baseline definition. In addition to the above, an access to the individual consumption of the stakeholders will be defined to facilitate the establishment of the virtual balances to be defined in the contract with the ESCO.

9.4 Specific Contracting implementation process steps

Having analysed the requirements of the CECs with respect to the integration of contracting structures and schemes, this section provides basic guidelines for the specific implementation of such structures in citizen energy communities. For this purpose, the integration methodology is based on the following scheme:

Figure 20: General scheme of the implementation of a contracting scenario into the CEC

9.4.1 Engagement

The ability to include a larger portion of the community in a meaningful way is critical to the accomplishment of any community-based goal. To effectively engage people and catch their attention in the topic of energy, you will first need to accomplish one of three goals: collect information, promote participation, or persuade individuals to take personal action on the topic of energy. When they are involved, a whole new universe of possibilities will present itself.

There are many different guises that actions of engagement might assume. One may put together their own gathering and distribute brochures all throughout the neighborhood. Utilizing pre-existing structures and occasions as a platform for further activity is still another method. Get yourself invited to speak at meetings of local groups, such as business networking, the Women's Institute, local political groups, scouts and guides, schools, lunch, and social clubs – whatever groups you can find in your local community, set up a stand at the local market, and get yourself invited to speak at those meetings. They will often be seeking for speakers, thus offering your services to them might be considered a favor.

By doing so, one is able to tap into already audiences, so reaching a greater number of people with a reduced amount of work and earning the "seal of approval" from preexisting groups, which will assist to legitimize your cause. In the meanwhile, you have the ability to dedicate more time to adapting your message to the specific audience you are speaking to in order to get them thinking and on your side.

9.4.2 Economical and financial analysis responsibility

The most relevant aspects with respect to the technical-economic analysis, specifically in reference to feasibility, and the financial analysis can be grouped into two main groups:

A technical-financial analysis of the citizen energy community must be carried out to analyze whether it is appropriate to carry out a contracting scheme or, failing that, the energy efficiency management can be carried out in such a way that there is no external intervention whatsoever. All this will depend on several aspects starting with the size of the system as well as the predisposition of the members of the community or the economic capacity of the same, the cultural principles rooted or not on sustainability and the preservation of the environment, etc. In any case, the commercial capacities of the companies providing

energy services as well as the situation of the energy market also converge at this point. If the engagement with respect to energy services is successful in the community, a technical-economic and financial analysis of the system must be carried out. There is no legal determination on the responsibility for action on such analysis, however, the recommendation is to use the services of a specific energy consulting company with a specific legal and fiscal office. If deemed appropriate, it may also be carried out by a qualified person who is a member of the energy community. This analysis will result in an assessment of the feasibility of implementing the energy efficiency service.

If the implementation of the contracting system is considered feasible and if the energy community approves its implementation, on the one hand, the selection of the company that will tender it (in case a competitive process is opened) or directly the corresponding ESCO is selected. With this ESCO, in the pre-phase of the project, the terms of the contract will be discussed as described in the previous sections. However, there is a very special differentiating point. The fiscal responsibility towards the ESCO and the financial institutions must be decided. Generally, the association or the corresponding legal entity is the one that must assume the responsibilities and in parallel, the legal entity of the energy community itself will define in its statutes the individual distributions of responsibility internally.

9.4.3 M&V specific aspects

Short-term electricity demand forecasting

Artificial neural networks are the most widely used technique for predicting short-term electricity demand in certain areas or cities. demand in the short term in certain areas or cities. Thus, different types of deep learning techniques are employed, such as feedback neural networks [23], recurrent neural networks [24], back propagation neural networks [25], autoencoders [26] or a combination of iteratively trained neural networks [27]. These networks are trained with historical power demand data (usually hourly), adding temporal variables such as day of the week, time of day or whether it is a holiday or not, and almost entirely consider temperature in some form.

Short-term wind power generation forecasting

Wind power forecasting techniques differ in the way the data is preprocessed. In the first case, wind speed data are decomposed into frequencies using different techniques such as hybrid mode decomposition [28] or adaptive secondary decomposition [29]. Then, the variance of the components obtained through different deep learning techniques is estimated. These models are fed with historical wind speed or wind power generation data, sampled at 10- or 15-minute intervals, and distributed by months or seasons to account for temporal variation. In the second case, the models are trained directly on the undecomposed wind speed or wind power generation data. The data collection frequency is usually hourly, 10-minutal or 15-minutal. Neural networks are the most used techniques [30], for example, the use of long short-term memory network (LSTM) [31] or fuzzy neural networks [32]; although other machine learning techniques [33] or hybrid models [37] are also employed.

Short-term photovoltaic generation forecasting

Solar power forecasting is mainly based on univariate series of global irradiance data with intervals of global irradiance data series with intervals between records of one hour or 5 min. used range from machine learning with decision trees or RFR to neural networks [34] or a combination of them [35].

However, it would have to be considered that the most efficient method depends on the variability of the irradiance data, i.e., the location [36].

9.4.4 Electric mobility

To combine the different possible techniques and provide the predictive algorithm with greater robustness, the concept of classifier ensemble will be adopted to the regression problem at hand.

A classifier ensemble is a classification model used in machine learning that consists of constructing a battery of classifiers for the same problem, where the final classifier is obtained by some combination or voting of the participating classifiers. The goal is for the resulting classifier to be better than each of the base classifiers that comprise it. The model responds to the same behavior as the essence of the human being and human reasoning that normally asks for opinions to different "experts" before deciding.

9.5 Financial and contracting scenario

As emerged, financing distributed renewable energy sources and energy efficiency interventions can be challenging work, even more complex in the context of CECs. Indeed, citizens' communities are perceived as with an inherently high risk, mainly due to several barriers pointed out in the previous chapter such as lack of knowledge and historical technical experience, difficulty to access finance and to access it at affordable prices, complicated planning and grid access process, lack of a clear legal framework and complex bureaucratic process, etc.

Focussing on the financial aspects, the most urgent barriers to address may be identified as follows:

- Financial challenges in the initial stages of project development.
- Ensuring fair and secure payments for energy generated (insufficient Feed-in-tariffs for wind, lack of standardized PPAs, third party-off take not possible).
- Complicated tax rules, no tax exemptions at energy community level.
- General lack of guarantees for RES projects.

The analysis of financial and contracting scenario is strongly linked to the peculiarity of each CECs: legal structure, level of involvement of the ESCO, EPC model chosen, type of actors involved.

CECs are legal entity, such as, for example, an association, a third sector body, a cooperative, a benefit cooperative, a consortium, a partnership involving a private company, or a non-profit organization. The ability to participate in a contract change based on the legal form chosen, at least regarding the decision-making process in selecting suppliers, services, and economic and financial conditions.

10 Internal Review

10.1 Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: Valentina Janev

Organisation: Institute Mihajlo Pupin

Date: 04/10/2022

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	Y			
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... contain an updated table of contents?	Y			
... contain a list of figures?	Y			
... contain a list of tables?	Y			
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y			
... contain an Executive Summary?	Y			
... contain a Conclusions section?	Y			
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?				Will be integrated

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?				Please check, it seems that it is OK
... use correct spelling and grammar?				Should be improved
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)				ok
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)	Y			
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy&paste text)				Should be improved
About the content...				
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	Y			
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	Y			
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	Y			
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	Y			
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	Y			
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		N		

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		N		
Are all references in the document included in the references section?				Will be
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		N		

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

	Document accepted; no changes required.
X	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5 (1 = poor, 5= excellent) – using a half point scale. Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
							4	

10.2 Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: Sara Tari

Organisation: SIF

Date: 06/10/2022

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	Y			
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?	Y			
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	Y			
... contain a version table?	Y			
... contain an updated table of contents?	Y			
... contain a list of figures?	Y			
... contain a list of tables?	Y			
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y			
... contain an Executive Summary?	Y			
... contain a Conclusions section?	Y			
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?				Yes, but it needs to be completed
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	Y			

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
... use correct spelling and grammar?				It needed some corrections
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)	Y			
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)	Y			
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy&paste text)				It could be better
About the content...				
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	Y			
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	Y			
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	Y			
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	Y			
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	Y			
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		N		
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		N		

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
Are all references in the document included in the references section?				Some of them still needs to be included, but only few
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (Copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		N		

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
46	7.3	The list of barriers could have been written in a more narrative way

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

☐	Document accepted; no changes required.
☒	Document accepted; changes required.
☐	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

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Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
							x	

11References

- [1] NADEL, S., & GELLER, H. (1996). Utility DSM: What have we learned? Where are we going? . Energy policy, vol. 24, no 4, 289-302.
- [2] STRID, M., & BERGMASTH, M. (2004). Energitjänster på en avreglerad marknad: För en effektivare energianvändning?
- [3] BLEYL-ANDROSCHIN, Jan W.; SEEFELDT, Friedrich; EIKMEIER, Bernd. Energy contracting: how much can it contribute to energy efficiency in the residential sector. ECEEE 2009 Summer Study Proceedings, 2009, p. 985-996.
- [4] DUPLESSIS, Bruno, et al. An empirical typology of energy services based on a well-developed market: France. Energy Policy, 2012, vol. 45, p. 268-276.
- [5] SHANG, Tiancheng, et al. A review of energy performance contracting business models: Status and recommendation. Sustainable cities and society, 2017, vol. 34, p. 203-210.
- [6] Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Energy End Use and Energy Services, 2006/32/EC, April 2016
- [7] LEE, P.; LAM, P. T. I.; LEE, Wai Ling. Risks in energy performance contracting (EPC) projects. Energy and Buildings, 2015, vol. 92, p. 116-127.
- [8] Energy Efficiency Services - Definitions & Requirements, EN-15900, January 2010.
- [9] Labanca, N., Suerkemper, F., Bertoldi, P., Irrek, W., & Duplessis, B. (2015). Energy efficiency services for residential buildings: market situation and existing potentials in the European Union. Journal of Cleaner Production, 109, 284–295.
- [10] LAFFONT-ELOIRE, K., et al. Sustainable business models for the deep renovation of buildings. Horizon, 2020.
- [11] SANTINI, M. et al. Pioneering a performance-based future for energy efficiency: Lessons learnt from a comparative review analysis of pay-for-performance programmes. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 2022, vol. 158, p. 112162.
- [12] SZINAI, Julia; BORGESON, M.; LEVIN, E. Putting your money where your meter is. Natural Resource Defence Council, 2017.
- [13] TZANI, Dimitra, et al. Pioneering a performance-based future for energy efficiency: Lessons learnt from a comparative review analysis of pay-for-performance programmes. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 2022, vol. 158, p. 112162.
- [14] SHABAN, H., “Who Wins the Pay-for-Performance Game? Measuring and Controlling Performance Risk,” in ACEEE Proceedings, 2018.
- [15] DENG, Qianli, et al. A simulation-based decision model for designing contract period in building energy performance contracting. Building and environment, 2014, vol. 71, p. 71-80.
- [16] DENG, Qianli, et al. Strategic design of cost savings guarantee in energy performance contracting under uncertainty. Applied Energy, 2015, vol. 139, p. 68-80.

- [17] MOZZO JR, Martin A. Setting the energy baseline for performance contracts. *Strategic planning for energy and the environment*, 2001, vol. 21, no 1, p. 12-19.
- [18] MARTIN, Lawrence L. Performance-based contracting for human services: Lessons for public procurement. *Journal of Public Procurement*, 2002, vol. 2, no 1, p. 55-71.
- [19] HUI, Sam CM. Opportunities, and challenges of energy performance contracting to improve existing buildings in Hong Kong. In *Proceedings of the Joint Symposium 2002: Achieving Sustainable Performance in Built Environment*. HKIE-BSD/CIBSE-HKB/ASHRA HK Chaper/Poly., 2002. p. 8-1.
- [20] DAVIES, Hilary A.; CHAN, Eric KS. Experience of energy performance contracting in Hong Kong. *Facilities*, 2001.
- [21] DREESSEN, T., 2003. Advantages and disadvantages of the two dominant world ESCO models; shared savings and guaranteed savings. In: Bertoldi, P. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the First Pan-European Conference on Energy Service Companies*.
- [22] POOLE, A.D., STONER, T.H., 2003. Alternative financing models for energy efficiency performance contracting. Sponsored by the USAID Brazilian Clean and Efficient Energy Program (BCEEP), administered by Winrock International.
- [23] YUAN, Qiangqiang, et al. Hyperspectral image denoising employing a spatial-spectral deep residual convolutional neural network. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 2018, vol. 57, no 2, p. 1205-1218.
- [24] HE, Yang, et al. soft filter pruning for accelerating deep convolutional neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.06866*, 2018.
- [25] YANG, Pengfei, et al. Enhancing robustness verification for deep neural networks via symbolic propagation. *Formal Aspects of Computing*, 2021, vol. 33, no 3, p. 407-435.
- [26] TONG, Zhan, et al. Videomae: Masked autoencoders are data-efficient learners for self-supervised video pre-training. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.12602*, 2022.
- [27] KHWAJA, Ahmed Shaharyar, et al. Joint bagged-boosted artificial neural networks: Using ensemble machine learning to improve short-term electricity load forecasting. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 2020, vol. 179, p. 106080.
- [28] ZHANG, Xin, et al. Cooperative coevolutionary bare-bones particle swarm optimization with function independent decomposition for large-scale supply chain network design with uncertainties. *IEEE transactions on cybernetics*, 2019, vol. 50, no 10, p. 4454-4468.
- [29] SUN, Shaolong, et al. Interval decomposition ensemble approach for crude oil price forecasting. *Energy Economics*, 2018, vol. 76, p. 274-287.
- [30] MASON, Karl; DUGGAN, Jim; HOWLEY, Enda. Forecasting energy demand, wind generation and carbon dioxide emissions in Ireland using evolutionary neural networks. *Energy*, 2018, vol. 155, p. 705-720.
- [31] YU, Yong, et al. A review of recurrent neural networks: LSTM cells and network architectures. *Neural computation*, 2019, vol. 31, no 7, p. 1235-1270.
- [32] SHARIFIAN, Amir, et al. A new method based on Type-2 fuzzy neural network for accurate wind power forecasting under uncertain data. *Renewable energy*, 2018, vol. 120, p. 220-230.

- [33] LANDRY, Tom, et al. Applying machine learning to earth observations in a standards-based workflow. En IGARSS 2019-2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium. IEEE, 2019. p. 5567-5570.
- [34] BENALI, Lamara, et al. Solar radiation forecasting using artificial neural network and random forest methods: Application to normal beam, horizontal diffuse and global components. Renewable energy, 2019, vol. 132, p. 871-884.
- [35] GALA, Karan, et al. 3DVAEReCNN: Region-based Convolutional Neural Network for Volumetric Rendering of Indoor Scenes. En 2022 2nd International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT). IEEE, 2022. p. 1-6.
- [36] FOUILLOY, Alexis, et al. Solar irradiation prediction with machine learning: Forecasting models selection method depending on weather variability. Energy, 2018, vol. 165, p. 620-629.
- [37] Camelo, Henrique do Nascimento & Lucio, Paulo Sérgio & Leal Junior, João Bosco Verçosa & Carvalho, Paulo Cesar Marques de & Santos, Daniel von Glehn dos, 2018. "Innovative hybrid models for forecasting time series applied in wind generation based on the combination of time series models with artificial neural networks," Energy, Elsevier, vol. 151(C), pages 347-357.